

MANAGEMENT OF MAJOR INSECT PESTS OF COWPEA: A REVIEW

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DECLARATION

I, the author of this dissertation do hereby declare that except for reference and quotation which have been duly accredited, this is a research carried out by me under the supervision of DR. Vincent Y. Eziah, a lecturer at the Department of Crop Science, University of Ghana, Legon. The work has not been submitted in full or in part for a degree anywhere. I am therefore merely responsible for any shortcomings, marginal or substantial which may be found in this work.

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to God Almighty, for the wisdom, knowledge and strength. He granted me throughout this research project. I also dedicate this work to my loving and supportive mother, Comfort Opoku for her encouragement and assistance. Finally, I dedicate this project to my family and friends who helped in any way to make this work a success.

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TABLE OF CONTENT

Contents

DECLARATION	ii
DEDICATION	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iv
TABLE OF CONTENT	v
LIST OF TABLES	viii
LIST OF FIGURES	ix
LIST OF PLATES	x
ABSTRACT	xi
CHAPTER ONE	1
INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1. Background.....	1
1.2. Problem statement	2
1.4. Objective.....	3
1.4.1. Research questions.....	3
CHAPTER TWO	4
2.0. LITERATURE REVIEW.....	4
2.1 Origin and geographical distribution of cowpea	4
2.2. Production of cowpea	5
2.3 Morphology and botany.....	8
2.4 Nutritional composition of cowpea	9

2.5 Economic importance of cowpea	10
2.6 Cowpea major insect pest	11
2.6.1. Maruca pod borer (<i>Maruca vitrata</i>).....	11
2.6.2. The bruchids (<i>Callosobruchus spp</i>).....	15
2.6.3. Cowpea aphids	18
2.6.4. Pod Sucking Bugs	21
2.6.5. Thrips	24
2.6.6. Foliage beetle	26
2.6.7. Leafhoppers (<i>Empoasca spp.</i>).....	27
2.7. The control of major insect pests of cowpea	29
2.7. 1 Chemical control.....	29
2.7.1.1. Synthetic insecticides.....	29
2.7.1.2. Botanicals.....	32
2.7. 2 Cultural control	37
2.7. 3 Host plant Resistance.....	41
2.7. 4Biological control.....	43
CHAPTER THREE	47
MATERIALS AND METHOD	47
CHAPTER FOUR.....	48
RESULTS.....	48
CHAPTER FIVE	71
DISCUSSION	71

CHAPTER FIVE	74
CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	74
5.1 Conclusion	74
5.2 Recommendation	74
REFERENCES	75

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Supply and demand of cowpea in selected west and central Africa (1990-1999).....	5
Table 2. Chemical composition of cowpea by FAO in 2004.....	9
Table 3. Mean number of insect pests and average yield of grains	48
Table 4. Mean score of the major pest of cowpea and yield obtained.....	55
Table 5. Mean score of major cowpea pest and yield obtained.....	56

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 chart showing cowpea production in Ghana from 2001-2016	8
Figure 2. Effects of different sprays of different insecticides on percent reduction in aphid over control.....	54

LIST OF PLATES

Plate 1 .adult of maruca pod borer	14
Plate 2 Lifecycle of maruca pod borer	14
Plate 3. A picture of adult callosobruchus maculatus	17
Plate 4 Lifecycle of callosobruchus maculatus	18
Plate 5. Adult of aphis craccivora	20
Plate 6. Pictorial image of both winged and wingless forms of aphids	21
Plate 7 A pictorial image of Nezara viridae	23
Plate 8. Adult of Riptortus dentipes	23
Plate 9 adult of Anoplocnemis curvipes	24
Plate 10. Flower bud thrip image	25
Plate 11. Lifecycle of the flower bud thrip	25
Plate 12 Adult of O. mutabilis foliage beetle.....	27
Plate 13. A pictorial image of a Leafhopper	28
Plate 14. Pictorial lifecycle of leafhopper	28

ABSTRACT

Vigna unguiculata commonly known as cowpea is an economically important staple crops in Ghana. It is extensively grown all around the world due to its outstanding benefits it provides. However, cowpea production is significantly limited below its potential. This is majorly due to the infestation of many insect pests during its development on the field and even during its storage. The major insect pests of cowpea are Aphids (*Aphis craccivora koch*), flower bud thrips (*Megalurothrips sjostedti trybom*), the legume pod borer (*Maruca vitrata*), foliage beetle (*Oothea mutabilis*), leafhopper and pod sucking bugs (*Anoplocnemis curvipes*, *Riptortus dentipes*, *Nezara viridia* and *Acanthomia spp*) and in store the major insect pest is *Callosobruchus maculatus* (cowpea beetle). These major insect pests of cowpea causes significant losses between ranging between 80 % - 100 %. This review therefore projects on the various updated control measures adopted in controlling these major insect pests and how they are integrated to provide the maximum efficacy.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Cowpea is one of the most propagated and staple leguminous crops grown worldwide especially sub-Saharan Africa particularly Ghana because of its ability to tolerate drought and improve soil organic matter. In Ghana, it is the second most important legume with groundnut being first. There are many benefits derived from cowpea production which include improving soil fertility through fixation of atmospheric nitrogen into soil through microbial activities. Its ability to be used in mixed and intercropping systems since it is compatible with a number of cereals and root crops such as sorghum, maize, millet and groundnut increases its significance in production systems. Cowpea can also produce high quality animal fodder and has a quick growth rate and rapid ground cover which makes it essential in regions with scanty rainfall and poor soils in organic matter such as the northern part of Ghana (Rachie, 1989). Cowpea is sometimes called “poor’s meal” because of its high nutritional content, protein 20-25%, carbohydrate 64% and essential amino acids such as lysine, riboflavin, valine and threonine. This increases the demand worldwide especially in developing countries in 2010, the demand was higher than the supply or production level leading to the importation of three thousand three hundred and eighty metric tonnes to supplement the produced quantity of two hundred thousand nineteen thousand and three hundred (Eghadzo *et al* , 2019). This indicates that the supply of cowpea is below its demand and there is low production of cowpea below its potential yield of 2.5 tonnes per hectare since the yield per hectare in Ghana is 1.3 metric tonnes in 2011. This also implies that the cowpea industry is challenged with many serious constraints both biotic and abiotic factors such as insect pest infestation, low fertility levels

and poor irrigation system and poor post-harvest methods which results in great post-harvest losses.

1.2. Problem statement

The most devastating constraint facing the cowpea industry is the infestation of insect pest both in store and on the field. These insect pests of cowpea causes drastic substantial economic losses to all the people involved in the food chain of cowpea production. The cowpea pest complex consists of its major insect pests on the field which are Aphids (*Aphis craccivora koch*), flower bud thrips (*Megalurothrips sjostedti trybom*), the legume pod borer (*Maruca vitrata*), foliage beetle (*Oothea mutabilis*), leafhopper (*Empoasca spp*) and pod sucking bugs (*Anoplocnemis curvipes*, *Riptortus dentipes*, *Nezara viridia* and *Acanthomia spp*) and in store is *Callosobruchus maculatus* (cowpea beetle). These major insect pests can individuals cause up to 100 % yield loss making their control a crucial aspect of cowpea production.

1.3. Justification

The management of the major insect pests of cowpea have heavily relied on the use of chemicals particularly synthetic insecticide. Although, synthetic insecticide have played a historical role in agriculture development in general and particularly management of insect pests of all economically important agricultural crops such as cowpea. Its use have been intensively stigmatized due to the adverse effect experienced as a result of the excessive usage of these chemicals. Some of the adverse effects are development of insect resistance, effect on non-target species health risks, food contamination. Also to significantly increase production of cowpea, an updated and easily accessible data on the various control measure adopted must be provided for farmers.

1.4. Objective

The main aim of this investigation is to provide an updated account of the various management strategies used to control and reduce the level of the infestation of the major insect pests of cowpea both on the field and in the store.

1.4.1. Research questions

- What are the major insect pests of cowpea on the field and in the store?
- What are some of the cultural measure adopted?
- What are some of the chemical control including botanicals adopted?
- What are some of the biological control measures also adopted?
- Are these measure used individually or are integrated?

CHAPTER TWO

2.0. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Origin and geographical distribution of cowpea

The name cowpea originated from the fact that the plant was an important source of hay for cows in the southeastern part of the United States. (Timko *et al.*, 2007). Other names which reflects traditional seeds and market classes developed over time in the southern United States are “southern peas”, “black eyed peas”, “field peas”, “pink eyes” and “crowders”. The wild cowpea *vigna unguiculata* spp. *Unguiculata var spontanea* is said to be the progenitor of cultivated cowpea (Pasquet, 1999 in Timko *et al.*, 2007). Cowpea evolved in Africa as wild cowpeas only exist in Africa (Tweneboah, 2000). Interestingly, West Africa appears to be the major center of diversity in cultivated cowpea forms and was domesticated by farmers (Ng and Padulosi, 1988). Timko *et al.*, (2007), concluded that the center of diversity of wild *Vigna* species is southeastern Africa. The second center of diversity is India where it was first introduced during the Neolithic period and preceded the Christian era (Perrino *et al.*, 1993: Timko *et al.*, 2007). Cowpea has been cultivated in the southern Europe at least since the 8th century BC and perhaps since prehistoric times. Cowpea was introduced to West Indies in the 16th century by Spanish and taken to the united states about 1700 (Pursglove, 1968 in Timko *et al.*, 2007). Yard long beans, a unique cultivar group of cowpea that produces very long pods. It is widely cultivated in Asia as a fresh green or “snap” beans evolved in Asia and it is rare in Africa landrace germplasm.

Currently, cowpea is extensively cultivated in the semi-arid tropics covering Asia, Africa, Brazil, the Caribbean’s, India and central and South America. The main cowpea producing countries in Africa include Nigerian, Niger, Burkina Faso, Ghana, Kenya, Uganda, Malawi and Senegal.

2.2. Production of cowpea

The estimated worldwide area under cowpea production is 14.5 million hectares of which Africa alone accounts for about 12.3 million hectares and West Africa accounts for 10.6 million hectares of the Africa's cultivated land (Singh *et al.*, 2003; Kebede and Bekeko, 2020). The harvested area amounts to the total annual production of 6.2 million metric tons globally. About 83.4% of the world's overall production of cowpea is from Africa with over 80% of Africa's production is from West Africa (FAO, 2016; Saka *et al.*, 2018; Kebeke and Bekeko, 2020). Nigeria is the larger producer and consumer of cowpea globally and West Africa. With its production of 2,137,900 metric tons in 2014, it accounted for 38.3% and 47.2% of global and west Africa production respectively (Saka *et al.*, 2018). Langyintuo *et al.*, 2003 analyzed that, Niger, Burkina Faso, Benin, Mali, Cameroon, Chad and Senegal are net exporters of cowpea well as Nigeria, Ghana, Togo, Cote d' Ivoire, Gabon and Mauritania are net importers. Langyintuo *et al.*, 2003 presented the supply and demand of cowpea in some African countries to evaluate their consumption and profit gained. This information have been presented in a table 1 and this also depicts the various production levels of the various countries.

Table 1. Supply and demand of cowpea in selected west and central Africa (1990-1999)

	Harvested area (1000 ha)	Average yield (t/ ha)	Production (1000 t)	Consumption (kg per capita per year)	Demand (1000 t)	Surplus/deficit (1000 t)
Nigeria	3425	0.494	1691	18	2160	-469

	Harvested area (1000 ha)	Average yield (t/ ha)	Production (1000 t)	Consumption (kg per capita per year)	Demand (1000 t)	Surplus/deficit (1000 t)
Niger	3268	0.110	359	1.5	16	343
Mali	322	0.244	79	1.5	16	63
Burkina Faso	201	0.777	156	1.5	16	140
Togo	135	0.28	38	9	41	-3
	100	0.64	64	9	55	9
Benin						
Senegal	95	0.34	32	1.5	14	18
Ghana	85	0.66	57	9	169	-112
Mauritania	52	0.33	17	2.5	25	-8
Cote d'Ivoire	40	0.50	20	1.8	28	-8
Chad	44	0.49	21	1.5	11	10
Cameroon	38	0.83	31	1.5	14	17
Total	7804	-	2526	-	2526	0

Negative figures imply demand exceeds supply.

Source: Langyintuo *et al.*, 2003

Over the last three decades, global cowpea production grew at an average rate of 5% with 3.5% annual growth rate in area and 1.5% growth in yield and the area expansion accounting for 70% of the total growth during this period (Boukar *et al.*, 2016 in Kebeke and Bekeko, 2020).

In Ghana, the production of cowpea is mostly done on subsistence level making it second to the production of groundnut. It is second to groundnut in terms of area under cultivation, quantity produced and consumed annually. There is always a supply deficit since the demand for cowpea is higher than the production leading to the importation of cowpea to meet the supply deficit. This was confirmed in 2010, when Ghana imported 3,380 metric tons to supplement the production of 219,300 metric tons. The inability of the industry to produce cowpea to meet the demand of the market can be associated to the constraints facing the farmers. Constraints include insect pests and diseases, Preference of consumers, poor soil fertility and intensive labour etc

Despite this, Ghana is the fifth highest producer of cowpea in Africa (TLII, 2012). The cultivation of cowpea in Ghana is carried out mostly in the transitional zone, guinea savannah zone of Northern, Brong Ahafo, Upper east and Upper west regions. The trend of production have been displayed in a graphical image in figure 1 which starts from the year 2001 to the year 2016. The common variety cultivated by farmers is the creeping and erect “beng pella”. Other cultivated cultivars of cowpea are “ayiyi”, “asontem” and “ormondoh” which are cultivated in small quantities and harvested often between September and October (Dari, 2008).

Figure 1 chart showing cowpea production in Ghana from 2001-2016

2.3 Morphology and botany

Vigna unguiculata (cowpea) is a warm season herbaceous annual crop with dark green, shinier and less pubescent leaves. Cowpea can have erect, trailing, climbing or bushy growth form. They are usually indeterminate under favorable condition but the type of growth form and habit can be determined by its genotypes and growing season. Cowpea stem may be striate or smooth with white, dirty yellow, pink, pale blue or purple coloured flowers. Flowers are arranged in raceme or intermediate inflorescence in alternate pairs. Cowpea undergoes epigeal germination and it produces pods. Pod shape may be erect, crescent-shaped or coiled containing usually 8 – 20 seeds per pod (FAO cowpea, 2004). Seeds size can vary between 2 mm – 12 mm with either smooth or wrinkled seed coat. Seed coat colour can be white, red, brown or black depending on the variety (Aveling, 1999 cited by FAO cowpea, 2004).

2.4 Nutritional composition of cowpea

Cowpea considered as a special component in the diets of most individuals especially small-holder farmers because the leaves, immature pods, fresh seeds and dry grains can be eaten. As the first crop to be harvested in semi-arid regions, cowpea is very important since it bridges the hunger gap that exist between cropping seasons of staple cereal crops offering farmers great flexibility (Wahaga, 2019). Cowpea is an outstanding member of the Fabaceae family because of its exceptional nutritional content and its other benefits such as provision of high quality fodder, early maturing and soil enrichment capacity to farmers. It is mostly recommended as foodstuff to help balance the nutritional status of consumers since it is a good source of proteins, mineral and vitamins (Dari and Tindan, 2016). It is estimated to contain 20-25% proteins, 64% carbohydrates and some nutritive elements such as amino acids example lysine, tryptophan, phenylalanine, valine, threonine and methionine (Modu *et al.*, 2010 in Neya *et al.*, 2015; USDA, 2004). FAO (2004) analyzed the chemical composition of cowpea and their result have been presented table 2.

Table 2. Chemical composition of cowpea by FAO in 2004

	Seeds	Hay	Leaves
Carbohydrate	56-66		8
Protein	22-24		4.7
Water	11	18	85
Crude fiber	5.9-7.3	9.6	2
Ash	3.4-3.9	6.2	
Fat	1.3-1.5	11.3	0.3
Phosphorus	0.15	2.6	0.06
Calcium	0.11-0.08		0.26
Iron	0.01		0.01

In Central and West Africa, dry cowpea grains are used for a variety of dishes; the Whole grain is mainly eaten with cereals or used as an ingredient in soups or stews, While milled cowpea is mostly used to make fritters or steamed cakes (Langyintuo *et al.*, 2003).In Ghana, the dry grains are processed into flour and a dough made out of the flour and deep fried to prepare “agawu” and “koose” which are served with maize or millet porridge (Hausa “kooko”).The dry beans are also boiled and served with “gari” and fried ripened plantain called “red-red” or boiled with rice popularly called “waakye” or make into another dish such as “apprepensa”, “gable”, “nyonbeeka”, “tubani”, “gora” and “nagbechinge” (maize and beans) (Tetteh, 2017).

2.5 Economic importance of cowpea

Cowpea is an important leguminous crop with great economic importance in areas where they are propagated especially in Africa with vast proportion of the population using it as food, animal feed and cash income (Langyintuo *et al.*, 2003). The leaves, immature pods, fresh pods, dry grains can be all marketed to generate income for farmers and traders. The leaves and haulm serves as high quality animal fodder used to feed animals to increase animal production. Furthermore, the increase in animal production leads to increase in income of farmers and other benefits such as increase in manure to increase soil fertility. Cowpea has the potential to improve soil fertility with its unique ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen even in very poor soils with pH range of 4.5-9.0 and organic matter $\leq 0.2\%$ (Babura and Mustapha, 2012) through its symbiotic relationship with mycorrhizae. It is compatible as an intercrop with cereals example sorghum, cassava, cotton and millet and with a number of root crops to diverse income source and reduce pest infestation. It

also has a quick growth rate and rapid ground cover which make it an essential as a cover crop to suppress growth of weeds and avoid soil erosion to avoid degradation and make agriculture sustainable. The stems and roots can be left to decay after harvesting to recycle nutrient and add organic matter to the soil to improve upon various characteristics of the soil. Processed cowpea food and snack well as fresh produced cowpea food serve as a source of income to many rural and urban traders especially women who are involved in the value chain of cowpea.

2.6 Cowpea major insect pest

Cowpea is susceptible to many field and storage pests which greatly hampers the production of cowpea globally especially in Ghana. Cowpea is susceptible to a range of pest and pathogen that attack during all of the growth phase from seeding to storing. These include insect pests, fungi, viruses, nematodes, weeds and bacteria. The major insect pests of cowpea are aphids, flower thrips, leafhoppers, Maruca pod borer, pod-sucking bugs. The major group of storage pest of cowpea is bruchids which entails *callosobruchus maculata* and *Bruchidus atrolineatus*.

2.6.1. Maruca pod borer (*Maruca vitrata*)

Maruca vitrata belong to the order *lepidoptera*, superfamily *pyraloidae* and family *Crambidae*. *M. vitrata* is one of the key and serious pest of cowpea. It is believed that the center of origin is Indo-malaysian region and also a large diversity of natural enemies are encountered in the region (Ba et al., 2019). Their infestation significantly reduces yield up to 80 % (Sharma *et al.*, 1998; Ba *et al.*, 2019). They are pantropical pests because of their range, destructiveness and distribution in the tropics and subtropics which also makes it an economically important key pest of cowpea. It has a wide distribution in the tropics and subtropics ranging from Africa to other countries in other continent such as china, New Guinea, USA. *M. vitrata* initially infest cowpea plant in the terminal

shoots which is normally 21 days after planting and later spread to other parts such as peduncle and stem.

The adult has dark brown body consisting of nine segment with body length ranging between 13 mm -25 mm. The female adults have a blunt tipped segment well as the males have a sharp or forked hairy abdominal tip and are slightly longer than that of the females. The adults are nocturnal with a life span ranging between 3 to 10 days. Ba *et al.*, 2019 analyzed that mating occurs between the fourth and twelfth hour of darkness with females normally mating once and males mating several times. Also, mating by adults reach its peak three days after female emergence from pupation. Emergence of larva occurs during the early evening since they are mostly nocturnal. Their lifecycle is normally completed between 30 – 35 days. The adult moths have a fuscous brown forewing with lunulate black – eyed white spot in the end of the cell. Also, a black-edged semi- hyaline band beyond the cell from below the costa can be seen. The hindwings are semi – hyaline white with a basal fuscous area and a spot at the upper angle of the cell. They also possess a marginal fulvous brown fuscous band from costa to vein with an inner irregular edge.

The gravid females oviposit on all aerial parts (vegetative buds, leaves, flower leaf axils) of the plants but lower surfaces are preferred. Under favorable conditions, up to 800 eggs might be laid within 3-14 days singly or in batches of 2 - 16. The eggs are greenish white in color when newly laid and later become yellow. They are also oval in shape and translucent with faint reticulate sculpturing on the chorion and measuring 0.65 mm and 0.45 mm (Ba *et al.*, 2019; Ganapathy, 2010; Sharma, 1998).

The larvae possess a translucent tube shaped body with a pair of dark brown spots on each segment with intensity varying with host. The larval stage consists of five instars stages lasting for 8 to 14

days. Adati *et al.*, 2004 cited by Ba *et al.*, 2019 argued that the instars can be identified by measuring its head capsule width with 1th instar ranging 0.16 mm – 0.19 mm, 2nd instar between 0.31 mm – 0.38 mm, 3th instar between 0.50 mm – 0.60 mm, 4th instar ranging 0.75 mm – 1.00 mm and the 5th instar ranging 1.25 mm – 1.33 mm. the larvae attacks the tender parts of the stem, peduncles, flower buds, flowers and green pods before moving to another plant. During this stage of each insect pest, about 4- 6 flowers are destroyed since they feed on the pistil and stamen and also the pods. It is known that, the 1th and 2nd instars feed on the flowers well as the 3rd, 4th and 5th instars bore into developing pods (Sharma, 1998; Ba *et al.*, 2019). They make holes in the pods and feed with their anterior half of their body inside the plant part (FAO cowpea, 2004). There is also a prepupal stage which lasts for 2 – 3 days. During this period, the spots on the segment disappears, feeds stops and larvae construct a gauze – like cocoon.

Pupa actively changes color from light brown to red brown and finally to dark brown which becomes mottled with black and yellow just before emergence of adult. The stage occurs in a silken cocoon attached to the plant or within pods or in the soil near the host plants and lasting for 3 – 14 days. The presence of a distinct ring on the last abdominal segment distinguishes the male pupa from the female pupa since it is absent in females. A virtual image of a matured female maruca pod borer have been displayed in plate I with the lifecycle displayed in plate 2.

Plate 1 .adult of maruca pod borer

Source: <https://www.plantwise.org.com>

Plate 2 Lifecycle of maruca pod borer

source: <https://www.plantwise.org.com>

2.6.2. The bruchids (*Callosobruchus spp*)

There are number of *callosobruchus* species found infesting cowpea. Some identified species are *Callosobruchus rhodesianus*, *Callosubruchus phaseoli*, *Callasobruchus chinensis*, *Bruchidius atronlineatus* and *Callosobruchus analis*. Among the *callosobruchus* spp, the most dominated and widely spread species is *Callosobruchus maculatus*. *Callosobruchus maculatus* is commonly known as cowpea beetle. *C.maculatus* is a colopeteran belonging to the family *chrysomolidae* and sub-family *Bruchidae*.

C. maculatus is an important field-to-store pest of cowpea that causes huge economic losses to farmers especially small-scale farmers and losses can be between 60 %-100 % during three to six months of storing unprotected grains (Chelav *et al.*, 2013; Fatima *et al.*, 2016; Idoko *et al.*, 2018).. Symptoms of their infestation include holes in grains, moldiness and weight loss of stored produce. It is known that *C. maculatus* originated from Africa and it is widely distributed in the tropics and sub-tropics including Asia, Europe, united states and sub-Saharan countries of Africa. Asian countries include India, Banglesh, Punjab, Iran, Kuwait, Sri Lanka and Turkey. Germany, Canada, Brazil, Peru and Venezuela are also countries with *C.maculatus* infestations. In Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Egypt, Ethiopia, Kenya, Niger, Nigeria and Tanzania are some countries facing challenges with *C.maculatus* infestation aside Ghana.

C. maculatus can be easily identified among other members of the specie *Callosobruchus* based on its appearance. The coloration on the elytra gives its distinguishing feature of the beetle. The adults are 3-4 mm long, reddish brown and slightly elongated compared to the typical rounded appearance of other members of its family. The adults have emarginated eyes along the inner edges where the antennae are inserted. Both sexes have slightly serrated antennae, a pair of distinct inner

and outer ridges on the ventral side of each femur. Each ridge bears a tooth near the apical end. There is black and gray marking on the elytra with two black spots near the middle. Bandara and Saxena (1995), distinguished *C. maculatus* males as having comparatively shorter abdomen and the dorsal side of the terminal segment is sharply curved downwards and inwards well as the females have comparatively longer abdomen and the dorsal side of the terminal segment is only slightly bent downwards. Also, the presence of strong marking on the elytra consisting of two large lateral dark patches mid-way along the elytra and smaller patches at the anterior and posterior ends leaving a pale brown cross-shaped area covering the rest distinguishes the male from the female. This is as males are much less distinctly marked.

The life cycle of *C. maculatus* begins when the matured female lays eggs on the surface of drying pods or seeds in storage. It can lay up to 110 eggs. The eggs are firmly glued to the surface of the seeds. The eggs are domed structures with oval bases, small in size, translucent grey and inconspicuous when newly laid. The egg hatches between 5-6 days after oviposition. Detritus produced is packed into the empty egg. This changes the egg colour to a whitish colour making it visible to the naked eye. The larvae upon hatching bites the base of the egg and the testa and enters into the seed. After entering pod or seed, it forbs on the cotyledon and feed until it attains maturity. The larvae feeds internally until it attains maturity and the adult emerges out of the seed. The larval and pupa stage lasts for about 15-21 days. The larva is whitish in colour. The larvae is not capable of migrating between seeds, therefore, oviposition behaviour of the female adult is crucial in determining the survival prospect of the progeny (Fatima et al., 2016). A pictorial image of the four stages it undergoes have been displayed in plate 4 which shows its egg stage, larval stage, pupal stage and its adult stage.

The adult does not feed making it last for mostly less than two weeks (14 days). The adult spends their limited lifetime to mate and lay eggs. Both the female and male can mate several times during their lifetime. An image of a matured adult bean weevil have been showed in plate 3. Fatima *et al.*, 2016 stated that oviposition rates are adjusted by the females in order to handle the changes in host availability and thus lays few eggs when host availability is low to reduce larval competition and enhance their survival. The optimum condition for their development is a temperature between 30⁰ C and 35⁰ C and a relative humidity of 70 % and 90 %.

Plate 3. A picture of adult callosobruchus maculatus

source: <https://www.shutterstock.com>.

Plate 4 Lifecycle of callosobruchus maculatus

source: <https://www.shutterstock.com>

2.6.3. Cowpea aphids

Cowpea aphids [*Aphis craccivora* Koch] which belongs to the family Aphididae, order *hemiptera* and sub order homoptera is one of the most disturbing economic and key pest of cowpea which causes damage from seedling stage to pod bearing stage [Bata *et al* , 1987 ; Singh *et al* ,1990]. Aphids are tiny, soft and silicate pear shaped insects with a velvety black and distinct waxy cover. They possess a fairly long antennae with a pair of compound eyes, jointed rostrum, two – segmented tarsi with a paired claws. They have black and white legs during all its life stages. They also possess a pair of dorsi – lateral which elongates into siphunculi at the end of the abdomen arising from the dorsal side of the fifth or sixth abdominal segment. This secretes a waxy fluid known as honeydew which results in the growth of sooty moulds. They have large wings which

are transparent with few veins and are held vertically above the body. An image of the adult have been displayed on plate 5 with a summary of its lifecycle displayed in plate 6.

There are two morphologically distinct forms of aphid adult which are the alate forms (winged form) and apterous forms (wingless forms). Aphids can undergo both sexual and asexually reproduction depending on the environmental conditions. Mostly under stressful conditions such as overcrowding and food shortage, the alatae forms are produced to enable them fly to other hosts to spread their infestation and reduce competition. Asexual reproduction to mostly undertaken by both apterae and alate females and bring forth live young nymphs. Aphids may live from 6-15 days and produce more than 100 progenies. Nymphs have a smoky or dull grey colour with length mostly up to 2 mm long. They molt and shed their skin four times to mature into reproductive adults within a few days. Molting and shedding occurs between the first instar to the adult stage.

Aphids causes both direct and indirect damage which results in qualitative and quantitative losses of seeds and crop produced. Aphids are polyphagous insects with piercing and sucking mouthpart which greatly influences their feeding habits. They are capable of modifying the metabolism of plants by extracting plant nutrients and indirectly by transmitting phytopathogenic viruses and interfering with biological control. Depriving of plants its nutrients, by sucking of the plant sap using its piercing and sucking mouthparts results in stunted growth, leaf shedding and yellowing of leaves. This further reduces photosynthesis significantly affecting yield. Aphids also transmit a number of viruses which also affects cowpea production. The most economically important viral cowpea disease is the cowpea aphid - borne mosaic virus which causes huge substantial yield loss. The secretion of honeydew which promotes the growth of sooty moulds and fungal growth well as invasion of ants infers the activity of natural enemies in the field reducing the efficiency of

biological control. This also affects photosynthesis since the sooty moulds covers the surface of leaves limiting the absorption of sunlight which is a vital prerequisite for photosynthesis. All this results in substantial yield loss up to 100 % in production [Singh and Allen, 1980: Singh *et al*, 1990: Babura and Mustapha, 2012].

Plate 5. Adult of aphis craccivora

source: www.googlechrome.com

Plate 6. Pictorial image of both winged and wingless forms of aphids

Source: <https://www.googlechrome.com>

2.6.4. Pod Sucking Bugs

The heteropteran pod-sucking bugs are the most important post flowering pests of cowpea (Taiwo *et al.*, 2016). The bug complex consists of members of the families *Coreidae* and *Alydidae* including *Anoplocnemis curvipes*, *Riptorttus dentipes*, *Acanthomiam spp* and *Nezara viridia* (Soyelu and Akingbohunbe, 2006).

Singh and Allen (1990), stated that *Anoplocnemis curvipes* causes 30 % to 70 % reduction in yield of cowpea and they can spread wide in the field as they are strong fliers. Adult bugs are black in colour with length up to 3 cm long. Its image have been shown on plate 9. The female adult lays its eggs in chains usually on leguminous trees or weeds but seldom on cowpeas. The eggs have a grey to black colour. In about 7 – 11 days, the eggs hatch into nymphs and they undergo five nymphal instar stages. During the early stages of the nymphal instars, they resemble ants and also it nymphal stages lasts for 29 – 54 days.

Acanthomia spp (*Acanthomia tomentosicollis* and *Acanthomia horrida*) may cause up to 90 % losses in cowpea yield. The adult of *A. tomentosicollis* is brown in colour well as *A. horrida* adult is grey in colour. Also, *A. tomentosicollis* have a compact furry body with short spines on the abdomen and *A. horrida* have a cylindrical body with longer spines on either side on the abdomen. With both bugs, eggs are laid on cowpea and are not widely distributed since they are not strong fliers on like *Anoplocnemis curvipes*. Consequently, a large of these bugs can be found on single pod.

Riptortus dentipes belong to the family *Alydidae*. Adults are cylindrical in shape with a light brown body colour and a distinct white or yellow lines on the sides of the body. An image have been displayed on plate 8. Eggs can be laid on cowpea, leguminous trees or weeds in short rows or scattered form. They are also strong fliers with five nymphal instar stages.

Nezara viridae belong to the family *Pentatomidae*. They have a triangular body which is green in colour. They have a life span usually between 30 days to 60 days. A matured female may lay up to 250 eggs in 4-6 batches. Eggs hatch into nymphs which are shiny with bright spots on their body and undergo five nymphal instar stages. Plate 7 displays an image of a *Nezara viridae*.

The different species of pod sucking bugs have their nymphs and adult feeding on the pods. They pierce and cut pod tissue with their stylet. This is done while injecting digestive enzymes through the salivary canal to liquefy the food into nutrient-rich slurry. The nutrient-rich slurry is then ingested through the food canal and passed into the alimentary canal for further digestion and absorption (Cohen, 2000 : Mitchell, 2000 cited in Taiwoo *et al.*, 2016 : Soyelu and Akingbohunge, 2006). Cellular and tissue damages are caused by the injected salivary enzymes. This leads to symptoms such as shriveling of developing pods, seed malformation in mature pods, drying of pods and half-filled pods.

Plate 7 A pictorial image of *Nezara viridula*

Source: <https://www.diArk.org.com>

Plate 8. Adult of *Riptortus dentipes*

Source: <https://www.googlechrome.com>

Plate 9 adult of *Anoplocnemis curvipes*

Source: <https://www.diArk.org.com>.

2.6.5. Thrips

Thrips (*Megalurothrips sjostedti*) belongs to the order *thysanoptera* and is also a major pest of cowpea. It attacks the buds, racemes and flower causing premature abortion of these reproductive organs. Yield losses ranges between 20%-100% (Hamadou *et al.*, 2018; Oparaeke *et al.*, 2006). Their infestation may sometimes cause changes in the nutritional composition of cowpea. Adults are extremely fecund and small making their control difficult. Their entire life cycle lasts for 14-18 days and an image have been shown in plate 11. Eggs are laid in the flower buds and nymphs feed extensively damaging the reproductive organs because they become discoloured and distorted and consequently aborted which substantially reduces yield. A picture of a foliage thrip have been presented on plate 10.

The pupae develop in the soil. Thrips have the ability to fly in masses helping them to spread widely since they can colonize many population in a short duration. Also, they have a wide range

of alternate hosts and tendency to develop insecticide resistance since they escape insecticide spray by hiding within the flower during spraying. Symptoms of thrip infestation include streak, silvery speckling and small patches, stunted with damaged flowers and fruits.

Plate 10. Flower bud thrip image

Source: <https://www.diark.org.com>

Plate 11. Lifecycle of the flower bud thrip

2.6.6. Foliage beetle

The beetles *Ootheca mutabilis*, *Medythia quaterna*, *Lagria villosa* and *Chrysolagria nairobana* are pre flowering insect pest of cowpea. Among the different species of foliage beetles, *O. mutabilis* is considered as the most important. Since it does not only cause direct damages but also it is a vector for an economically important virus. *O. mutabilis* can reduce yield by 27 % up to 100 % by attacking foliage soon after germination. It transmits the yellow mosaic virus which also can cause total yield loss under severe infestation.

The adult beetle is usually reddish brown in colour although they can be either brown or black in colour. Their length varies between 5.4 mm – 7.3 mm which females mostly between 5.6 mm – 6.7 mm and male between 5.4 mm – 7.3 mm. The matured female deposit its eggs in the soil close to the host plant. The eggs are translucent yellow in colour and hatch into larvae. The larvae thereafter undergoes 3 larval instars while feeding on the roots of the cowpea seedling. It noted that the first instar larvae feeds on the nodules around the roots by boring into them. The second instar larvae destroys the roots nodules by damaging the epidermal tissues of the lateral roots which leads to wilting of plant and finally death. The larvae then pupates into a yellow coloured pupae and this occurs in the soil.

It is known that their lifecycle takes between 61-100 days and undergo diapause during their second generation. After diapause, adult eclosion normally coincides with germination of early planted cowpea seeds. *O.mutabilis* infestation can cause total destruction to the extent of death of

seedling since adult feed interveinally on the young leaves while the larvae feed on the roots of the cowpea plant.

Plate 12 Adult of *O. mutabilis* foliage beetle

Source: <https://www.shutterstock.com>

2.6.7. Leafhoppers (*Empoasca spp.*)

The most important species are *Empoasca kerri* in Asia, *Empoasca dilichi* in Africa and *Empoasca Kramori* in central and south America (Singh and Allen, 1990). They belong to the family Cicadellidae and sub - order Homoptera and order Hemiptera. Adult have normally have a body length between 3 – 4 mm with short wings (Brachypeterous). Its image have been shown on plate 13. Adult leafhoppers have a lifespan ranging between 30 – 60 days depending on the host, species and environmental conditions with females usually living longer than males. Females have a prominent ovipositor located at their posterior end. The eggs are laid underside of leaves and nymphs hatch within 7-10 days. During the nymphal development, there are five instar stages which lasts for 10 days after which the adult appears. With length of the first, second, third, fourth and fifth instar nymphs being 0.69 mm, 1.09 mm, 1.34 mm, 1.68 mm and 2.28 mm respectively. A summarized image of its lifecycle have been presented on plate 14. They infest cowpea at the

seedling stage and symptoms are yellow discoloration of leaf veins and margins, stunted growth and premature death of plants.

Plate 13. A pictorial image of a Leafhopper

Source: <https://www.googlechrome.com>

Plate 14. Pictorial lifecycle of leafhopper

Source: <https://www.googlechrome.com>

2.7. The control of major insect pests of cowpea

Cowpea is an important staple crop in Ghana with diverse and great economic benefits. It is attacked by during every stage of development from seedling to maturity and even in storage. Therefore, it is very crucial to control insect pests since they can cause up to 100 % yield loss. The major insect pests of cowpea are aphids, leafhoppers, pod borers, pod sucking bugs and foliage beetles on the field and cowpea beetle in store. Various control measures have been adopted to curtail their infestation of cowpea crops on the field and in the store. These measure involves cultural control measures, the use of chemical both synthetic and botanicals, biological control and host plant resistant strategies.

2.7. 1 Chemical control

2.7.1.1. Synthetic insecticides

The use of synthetic chemicals is considered the most efficient and mainstay of agricultural pest control. Its use have made great historic impact in the field of insect control. The efficacy of synthetic chemicals can be done both in laboratory and on the field. In the laboratory, bioassay such as leaf dip method, topical method, contact method, film, residue method or fumigation method are conducted to evaluate the toxicity of insecticides against insect pests. It generates comparative toxicity data on a wide range of chemicals in the shortest possible time. It is simple, cost effective and readable making it the quickest and easiest way to evaluate insecticidal efficacy

of many chemicals. On the field, chemicals are tested to determine the right concentration and rate most effective against insect pests. The most appropriate time to apply insecticide is also determined. Most chemicals have been proven to be effective the major insect pests of cowpea. Chemicals include cypermethrin, alphaeypermethrin, deltamethrin and lambdacyhalothrin based synthetic pyrethoids insecticides have been tested against major cowpea insect pests.

Opolot *et al.*, 2006 stated that cypermethrin is effective against flower bud thrips because spraying of cowpea plants with cypermethrin significantly reduced its infestation level. Spraying was done at budding and flowering stages of the crop. Furthermore, they concluded that spraying five times with cypermethrin not only control thrips but also pod sucking bugs, legume pod borer and cowpea beetle but does not prevent the total transfer of cowpea beetle to storage.

Ba *et al.*, 2019 explained that, a great portion of chemicals such as DDT used to control the legume pod-borer are not recently. But, there are a number found to be effective against the legume pod-borer *M. vitrata* such as organophosphate, lambdacyhalothrin, deltamethrin and cypermethrin. They also stated that in Nigeria, the most effective approach against *M. vitrata* is spraying twice with lambda-cyhalothrin or cypermethrin combined with dimethoate.

According to Ganapathy (2010), controlling of the major insect pests of cowpea can be done using four high volume spray of cypermethrin at a concentration of 0.008 %. The spraying times is argued on where initial flowering, 50 % flowering, 100 % flowering and 100 % pod setting.

Opolot *et al.*, 2006 stated that, control of cowpea pests can be achieved when sprayed with a mixture of dimethoate (40 EC) applied at 200 g ai/ha and cypermethrin at 250 g ai/ ha.

Sharma *et al.*, 1998 also explained that, spraying twice with endosulfan applied 35 days after planting at weekly intervals, one spray of cypermethrin, cyhalothrin, bipenthrin and in combination with dimethoate or two applications of cypermethrin and dimethoate at 10 days intervals beginning at bud formation can be used to control the major pests of cowpea on the field.

The efficacy of dichlorvas 76 % EC (0.076%), imidacloprid 17.85 l (0.00712%), dimethoate 30 % EC (0.06%), chlorantraniliprol 18.5 SC (0.0037 %) and thiamethoxan 25 WG (0.003%) was evaluated against aphids and other major insect field pest of cowpea by Elango *et al.*, 2009. They discovered that, mortality caused were 96.6 %, 94.4 %, 92.2 %, 84.4 % and 83.3 % respectively after 48 hours. This implies that, the use of these chemicals can significantly reduce the population of aphids on cowpea limiting their effects mainly yield loss caused.

During storage, the main kind of synthetic insecticide mostly used are fumigant emulsifies such as phosphine, methyl bromide, delta methrin and Malathion (Sanon *et al.*, 2018). Most farmers in Ghana also use agrochemicals such as Malathion, perfekthion 20 EC, atelic and cymbush to control *C. maculatus* (Tweneboah, 2000).

Chelav *et al.*, 2013 illustrated that diatomaceous earth which is a fossilized remains of diatoms that forms inert dust can significantly control *C. maculatus* in store by increasing mortality and reducing progeny production. This was investigated when adult *C. maculatus* came into contact with the small particle of the dust, the waxy layer of the cuticle absorbed the small particles resulting in water loss, desiccation and death. Also, it is known that when mortality is high, damage incurred is significantly reduced since oviposition and progeny emergence is drastically reduced (Subramanyam *et al.*, 2000; Stathers *et al.*, 2004 cited in Chelav *et al.*, 2013). The use of inert dust to control *C. maculatus* have been registered in many countries such as USA, Japan, Croatia,

Australia, Brazil, China, Germany and other countries since it is considered low toxic to mammals (Stather *et al.*, 2004 cited by Chelav *et al.*, 2013).

2.7.1.2. Botanicals

The use of plant materials to control insect pest's populations on cowpea of agricultural is considered as a promising alternative to synthetic insecticide (Idoko *et al.*, 2018; Sanon *et al.*, 2018). Plants material such as powders, essential oils and extracts may produce volatile chemicals that may be toxic or repel the major insect pests of cowpea reducing the damages incurred during production or in store. While as, others produce secondary metabolites that directly affect development and reproduction of the major insect pests. Botanicals are also relatively harmless to non- target organisms, biodegradable, cheaper, environmentally friendly and low development of resistance.

Oparaeke (2006) explained that, crude extracts from plants (powder, water extracts, oils and wood ash) have been widely used by farmers to control the major insect pests of cowpea since different active ingredients which confer for different pesticidal such as attractants and oviposition deterrents activity have been observed. Also, Manzoor *et al.*, 2011 explained that, a variety of properties have been shown by plants extract which includes, insecticide activity, repellency to pests, antifeedants effects, insect growth regulation, toxicity to other biological pests such as nematodes, mites, fungi and bacterial. These properties increase the potential of plant extracts in controlling these major insect pests of cowpea both on the field and in store.

On the field, a range of botanicals have tested and its efficacy in managing the major insect pests have established. For instance, *Piper guineense*, *Artocarpus altilis*, *Aframomum melegueta*, *Carica papaya* and neem- based preparations have been tested against insect pests of cowpea ranging from

pre flowering insects to podding insects pest. Ganapathy, 2010 explained that some extracts act as antifeedant preventing their infestation. Plants extracts include extracts from neem seed kernels and chilli fruits which showed high deterrent effects against these major insect pests on the field when sprayed or when the applied as dust in its dried form around the cowpea plants significantly reduced the infestation of the legume pod borer. This significantly increased the grain yield of cowpea obtained.

This was confirmed when different concentration of emulsifiable concentrate (5 %, 10% and 20 %) was used against *M. vitrata* and high degree of its toxic effects was observed (Jackai and Oyediran, 19991). Also, the efficacy of neem against aphids was shown by Elango *et al*, 2009 by proving that, 54.4 % and 51.1 % mortality was caused when extracts from its leaves at 1000 ppm(0.02%) and its seed kernel 5 % was sprayed and recorded after 48 hours. This also shows that, there will be an increase in mortality will be observed when concentration is increased to significantly control aphids. Furthermore, the efficacy of extracts from the seeds and leaves of neem against pod sucking bug complex have been established even though the seed extract gave better results than the extract from the leaves (Okolo and Oyewole, 2019).

Oparaeke (2006) established the efficacy of *piper guineese* against flower bud thrips by evaluating the pod density per plant on different plots sprayed with 5 %, 10 % and 20 % (w/v) extract of the botanical. He then discovered that, the pod density per plant was significantly high for the plots sprayed with 10 % and 20 % extract of *piper guineese* at a spraying time of two, four and six weekly interval starting from flower bud formation at a rate of 150 l/ ha. This is because, flower bud thrip infestation pressure was reduced in these plots when compared with those sprayed with 5 % extract concentration.

The potential of *Azadirachta indic*, *Chromolaena odorata* and *Ricinus communis* as an insecticide against pod sucking bug complex (*Anoplocnemis spp*, *Riptortus spp*, *Clavigralla spp* and *Nezara viridula*) using its leaf extract have been established (Degri et al., 2013). They observed that, even though all three species were effective against the pod sucking bugs, *Ricinus communis* was relatively less effective than *A. Indica* and *C. Odorata*. This was correlated from the results obtained from the various plots sprayed with *A. Indica*, *C. Odorata*, *R. Communis* and water as control using the yield, number of pods and weight of pods. With the number of pods and weight of the pods observed, *Azadirachta indica* and *Chromolaena odorata* had 23-25 pods and 14-15 g, *R. Communis* had 21 pods and 13 g with the control plots gave 16 pods and 9 g respectively. Consequently, the grain yield obtained from plots sprayed with *A. Indica* and *C. Odorata* were four times that of the control well as *R. Communis* was three times more than the yield obtained from the control plots. Also, the spraying of the plots was done fortnightly beginning on the onset of pods using 5% w/v concentration of leaf extract.

The effect of some cereal (sorghum, pearl millet and maize) and legume (Cowpea and soyabean) extract against pod sucking bugs through the inhibition of protease enzyme activity was investigated (Taiwo *et al.*, 2016). They discovered that, the legumes were more effective in controlling the pod sucking bug complex than the cereals by reducing the damage incurred as a result of their infestation. *Azadirachta indica* seed extract is also known to be effective against the foliage beetls particularly *O. mutabilis*.

Furthermore, in the store various botanicals have also been tested against *C. maculatus* since it is the major insect pest of cowpea during storage. Essential oils from plants are mostly used in protecting cowpea grains during storage since it can be used as both contact and synthetic

insecticide against stored insect pest particularly *C. maculatus* which is the major pest in store (Osekere, 1998; Ogboanna *et al.*, 2016; Oliveria *et al.*, 2018). The mode of action has been argued as to be very diverse ranging from physical through repellency action to chemical toxicity to all stages of insect development (Osekere, 1998; Ogboanna *et al.*, 2016; Oliveria *et al.*, 2018). The oils enters the spiracle and trachea of *C. maculatus* causing asphyxiation and therefore death. They also hypothesis that occlusion effect by some oils is the reason for their ovicidal and larval effects. Its mode of action as ovicide can be related to infiltrating under the opercium and blocking respiration or disrupt the water balance of eggs and developing embryos (Osekere, 1998).

Brito *et al.*, 2006 cited in Oliveria *et al.*, 2018 evaluated, the toxicity of essential oils from Eucalyptus spp. On *C. maculatus* and observed reduction in lethal time and lethal concentration at 50 with increase in exposure time and doses. The efficacy of essential oil also from *thymus persicus* against *C. maculatus* was investigated by Saroukolai *et al.*, 2013. They discovered that over 88 % mortality was recorded when *C. maculatus* was exposed for 24 hours to 9.8 µl/ L air. T

In addition, the essential oil of plants from the citrus genus and its components have also shown insecticidal activity against *C. maculatus* (Dutra *et al.*, 2016 cited in Oliveria *et al.*, 2018). In addition to these essential oils, Nwankwo *et al.*, (2009) proved that, *Azadirachta Indica* seed oil cause increase in mortality leading to reduction in the number of eggs laid and therefore emergence and number of holed cowpea seeds. *Azadirachtin* is the active ingredient of neem extracts and it acts as an anti-ovipositant, adulticide and larvicide which has been well established for the control of *C. maculatus*. Oliveria *et al.*, 2018, investigated the repellency potential of essential oils from *Schinus terebinfolius*, *Piper aduncum*, *Syzygium aromaticum*, *piper hispidinervum*, *Cymbopogon citratus* and *Cinnamomum zeylani*. They confirmed that among the selected plants, S.

aromaticum and *P. hispidnervum* has the potential to repel *C. maculatus*. They then used gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometer to find out its active ingredients which were safrole and eugenol respectively.

The use of dried powders from plants has also been used to analyze to establish its efficacy by many researchers. Dried powder of *Zingiber officinale* was used by Ogbonna *et al.*, 2016 to evaluate its efficacy against *C. maculatus*. They discovered that, it exhibits various levels of toxicity by acting as an anti-feedant. Also the higher the concentration, the more significant its efficacy. This agrees with the research done by Bamphitlhi *et al.*, 2014 on reproduction and damage of *C. maculatus* using garlic, peppermint and chilies. They discovered that chilies and garlic had negative effects on the reproduction and damage since it substantially increases mortality but less effect was recorded for peppermint. The effectivity of ashes and powders of some plants was also established by some researchers.

This is in accordance with the finding of Dari, 2008, who proved that wood ash from mahogany (*Khaya senegalensis*) and dried powdered orange peel can remarkably control *C. maculatus* during the first six months of storing cowpea without compromising its' viability and quality. Idoko *et al.*, 2018, showed that the powder of both ripped and unripe pawpaw seeds can act as an insecticide against *C. maculatus*. When 0.8 g/ 20 kg of concentration was used for both powder of ripped and unripe pawpaw seeds, 83.3 % and 100 % mortality was recorded respectively. A plausible explanation for the difference in mortality can be attributed to the converting of the insecticidal chemicals during the ripening process to less harmful ones. Extracts from *Hemizygia welwitschii* using different solvent (hexane, acetone and methanol) was also tested, and the results proved that all the solvent were effective against *C. maculatus* at the highest dosage 10g/kg (Fotso *et al.*, 2019).

They furthermore concluded that, the higher the concentration and exposure time, the more effective the control. This is concordance with findings of other researchers (Bamphitlhi *et al.*, 2014; Ogbonna *et al.*, 2016; Nwankwo *et al.*, 2009).

2.7. 2 Cultural control

Cultural control is the oldest method of controlling the major insect pests of cowpea. However, its measures are preventive rather than curative. There are a number of researchers who researched into the effects of various cultural control measures such as planting time, spacing, harvesting time and weed control on the level of insect pest infestation. It is known that cultural control measures cause physiological changes that reduce the suitability of host plants for phytophagous insects.

Intercropping of cowpea with other compatible crops is widely used in Ghana since most cowpea production in Ghana is done on a subsistence level. Intercropping of cowpea with other crops such as maize, sorghum, cassava and millet results in crop diversity, lower temperature, higher relative humidity and reduced light transmission or penetration into canopy formed by crop. Results obtained from intercropping cowpea with other crops is said to be variable and dependent on environmental conditions as well as other control measures adopted. This can be associated to the increase on the level of infestation by some insect pests.

This agrees with the results obtained by Kampala *et al.*, 1999 that, intercropping cowpea with sorghum alone did not provide sufficient control against cowpea pests particularly aphids well as combining intercropping with foliar and seed dressing insecticide greatly increased yields. Gianessi (2013) also reported that intercropping of cowpea controlled aphids but had no effect on thrips, maruca pod borer and pod-sucking bugs because high plant density and early infestation reduces aphid infestation. Cited in Kusi *et al.*, 2019, Matteson 1982 said that intercropping cowpea

with maize reduces the population of thrips on the field. Sharma, 1998 stated that intercropping with maize lead to build up pod borer population but planting cowpea 12 weeks after planting maize reduces the pod borer population and also intercropping cowpea with sorghum and maize as maize-cowpea-sorghum also helps with reducing of insect pests on the field.

Planting dates and spacing has been established to some extent to affect or influence the level of insect pest infestation on the field. Sowing of cowpea early enable plants to escape most field insect pests attack and help develop pseudo resistance. Sharma and Ortiz (2002) explained that early sowing of cowpea leads to variation in temperature, photoperiod and other environmental conditions that affect establishment of insect pests on hosts and this phenomenon is known as pseudo resistance or false resistance. Spacing affects the plant density which in turn have as effect on the insect pest population on the field. Sharma, 1998 stated that early sowing of cowpea enables plant begin flowering before peaking of aphid population using they are most susceptible during the flowering stage to aphids. Also, dense crop canopy of cowpea plant by using high sowing rate help to deter aphid landing therefore reducing their population. Ba et al, 2019 also concluded that planting early significantly reduced infestation of insect pests on the field. Also, an experiment conducted by Karungi *et al.*, 2000a proved that planting on the on-set of rains at a density of 30 cm by 20 cm or 60 cm by 20 cm which gives a plant population of 183.333 plants/ ha and 100.000 plants/ha was better when assessed against 90 cm by 20 cm and 120 cm by 20 cm that plant population of 66.667 plants/ha and 50.00 plants/ ha respectively for effect caused by cowpea insect pests. They related this to the interference of visual stimulation of aphids caused by the dense crop population leading to reduced colonization and fecundity. It also known that early planting of cowpea helps it to escape periods of heavy infestation. Contrary to their finding, Kanteh et al.,

(2014) stated that planting density of 50 cm by 30 cm was most appropriate for controlling aphids as well as foliage beetle.

The use of trap crops and insect traps to attract cowpea insect pests on the field. Trap crops are crops planted in at specific parts of the field to attract insect pest and prevent or minimize their damage on target crops. After insect pests infest trap crops, they are then easily controlled since they are concentrated on the trap crops. Sharma, 1998 stated that *crotalaria spp* can be used as trap crops of maruca pod borer. This attracts the female moths to deposit their eggs on them when the trap crops are planted early on the field bunds. Also when insect traps such as pheromone traps are used, level of infestation of cowpea insect pests are reduced. Ba et al., 2019 used pheromone traps of EE10, 12-16: Ald and EE10, 12-16: OH as major and minor components respectively and a third component being (E)-10 hexadecenal (E10-16: ALD) was successful when used as lure and kill trap against maruca pod borer. Cited by Ba *et al*, 2019, the most effective lure and kill trap against maruca pod borer was a water trap made from 5 l plastic jerry-can placed at 120 cm height with lure attracting for 2 weeks (Downham *et al.*, 2004). The lure and trap such as yellow sticky trap and protein bait can also be used for monitoring of cowpea insect pests on the field.

Weed control, good farm hygiene and removal of alternate host plants. Cowpea insect pests have sources that serve as alternate host that they infest and harbor to over season when cowpea is out of season. Kusi *et al.*, 2019 discussed that most resource poor farmers combine good farm conditions such as regular weed control measures to help minimize insect pests' infestation on the field. Also, pod sucking bugs can be hand-picked and killed under low infestation and small plots. To control foliage and aphids infestation on the field, weeding twice at three and six weeks after planting reduces their infestation (Kanteh 2014).

Harvesting of pods should be done at the appropriate time and frequency to reduce or prevent initial infestation of the field since *C. maculatus* is a field-to-store pest (Chelav *et al.*, 2013; Fatima *et al.*, 2016). That is, harvesting of pods should be done before they completely dry and split open. This significantly reduces substantial damage or prevent infestation of the produce since the adult female first lays its eggs on drying pods on the field prior to harvesting and into store after harvesting. Also, sorting of grains should be done before storage to remove field infested grains from the stock and frequent inspection of stored grains should also be carried out. In stores, the racks used, corners and floors must be kept clean during storage and disinfested prior to storage.

The adoption of hermetic storage technology for storing cowpea also helps since the type of storage structure influences the level of infestation and thus level of damage incurred. Hermetic storage is a chemical-free and cost-effective way of controlling insect during storage to maintain grain quality and therefore its adoption can be very sustainable in Africa (Aboagy *et al.*, 2017). Hermetic storage principally occurs in controlled environment which continuously depletes oxygen levels and simultaneously increases carbon dioxide as a result of respiratory activities. The research on hermetic storage technology has led to the development of triple bagging technology with PICS (Purdue improved cowpea storage) bags (Dari, 2008; Aboagye *et al.*, 2017). This technology was developed by Purdue University in collaboration with Africa researchers and is widely used as an alternative to synthetic insecticide and metal silos. A PICS bag is composed of three layers: two inner layers of high density polyethylene and an outer layer of ordinary woven polypropylene. This works by suffocating adult and larvae to death and can protect grains up to three months without compromising its quality (Dari, 2008).

2.7. 3 Host plant Resistance

The relative amount of heritable qualities possessed by a plant or its material an example being its seeds which influences the extent to which damages are caused by an insect is known as host plant resistance (Ahmed and Yusuf, 2007). Host plant resistance is said to be an effective, economic, socially acceptable and environmentally friendly method of controlling insect pests (Sharma and Ortiz, 2002). It does not require some special level of know-how or application techniques and no cash investment making it most appropriate and sustainability to most farmers specifically resource poor farmers. Sharma and Ortiz (2002) explained that Host plant resistance is the adaptive and heritable feature of plants against insect pests that enable the plant to avoid or inhibit host selection, oviposition, feeding of insects on them. It also reduces or limits insect's survival and development on them as well as ability to recover or tolerant damage or injury caused by these insect pests.

Expression of resistance by plants is dependent on some factors mainly insect density and environmental conditions. Host plant resistance can be derived from physiochemical characteristics of plants which influences the behavior and biology of insects. For instance a number of seeds are said to be resistant to *C. maculatus* based on the possession of some chemicals that inhibit *C. maculatus* establishment on them. Chemical include, Trypsin inhibitors, Tannins, chitinases, insecticide lentins and Beta-1, 3- glucanases with a typical example been the possession of Alpha-amylase inhibitors by *Phaseolus vulgaris* prevents the development of *C. maculatus* on its seeds. Plant resistance is relative since the level of resistance is expressed in relation to other plants of the same species when grown under similar environmental conditions. It is expressed in terms of damage and injury incurred by plants during infestation of insect pests and the level of tolerance and recovery exhibited by the resistant genotypes.

Some genotypes and cultivar are known to have some level of tolerance or resistance against a number of cowpea insect pests but usually not all cowpea insect pests. It is known that the only cultivar highly resistant against *M. vitrata* is the wild vigna *Vigna vexilata* (Ba *et al.*, 2019; Mehinto *et al.*, 2020). Kusi *et al.*, 2019 conducted an experiment in the sudan and guinea savannah zones of Ghana located in the northern parts of the country to assess the tolerance level of different cultivars in combination with insecticide spraying times. IT99K-573-1-1 (resistant to striga, drought and macrophomina with a potential yield of 2.4 tons/ha), IT99K-573-2-1 (striga resistant, drought and macrophomina tolerant and known as in Ghana as wangkae and also has aphid resistant gene), songotra (low tolerance to macrophomina and resistant to striga), Padituga (drought and macrophomina tolerant), Bawutuwuta (striga tolerant with moderate to low resistance to insect pests and disease and a farmer's cultivar widely grown in the region were the genotypes they assessed. They discovered that Bawutuwuta, Songota, IT99K-573-1-1, IT99K-573-2-1 were tolerant to thrips because despite the high level of thrip infestation, relatively high yield were obtained as a result of quick replacement of trip-damaged or abscised flower.

The genotypes TVu's 59, TVu's 123 and VITA-3 are resistant to leafhopper, TVu's 1509, TVu's 2870, TVu's 6507 and TVu's 7133 resistant to flower bud thrips and TVu's 946 and VITA-5 are resistant to maruca pod borer (Singh and Allen, 1980). Oparaeke *et al.*, (2006) stated that, the genotypes TVu59, TVu 123, VITA-1 and VITA-3 were resistant to the infestation of leafhopper.

This was also confirmed by Abudulai *et al.*, 2017 when they reported that genotype IT99K-573-2-1 and IT99K-573-1-1 were less susceptible to most economic pest of cowpea (Kusi *et al.*, 2019). Kusi *et al* (2019) again stated that, the different genotypes exhibited different level of resistance against the pod sucking bugs while producing appreciable yield. The cultivar Zaayura which is

widely cultivated in the northern region of Ghana as it has high resistance against aphids (Wahaga, 2019).

Also, varieties that produce protease inhibitors should be adopted and planted to minimize the effects of pod sucking bugs infestation since protease is an enzyme produced by the bugs during feeding. This results in tissue damage because it is a digestive enzyme that breakdown cells in the pod tissue for the absorption of nutrients. The effect of protease production of plants was established by Taiwo et al. (2016) and they also investigated the effect and production of protease inhibitors by some cereal (sorghum, pearl millet and maize) and legume (Cowpea and soyabean) to minimize pod sucking bugs infestation effects. They therefore concluded that the legumes were more effective than the cereals and thus varieties that produce high levels of protease inhibitors should be used for cultivation.

2.7. 4 Biological control

There is a wide range of natural enemies against the major insect pest of cowpea. Natural enemies can be classified into three groups which are predators, parasitoids and entomopathogens. These groups of natural enemies can be used both on the field, in store and in the laboratory to control pests while maintaining biodiversity and reducing production cost.

Entomopathogenic organisms are fungi, bacteria, protozoa and viruses. To some extent, entomopathogenic organisms have been tested against insect pests. Ganapathy (2010) argued that, the rate or percentage of control of insect pests using pathogens can be said to be 30 %. A number of these entomopathogenic organisms have been tested and found effective against the major insect pests of cowpea.

The most common entopathogenic fungi used against most of the major insect pest of cowpea is *Beauveria Bassiana*. It has been tested against aphids, maruca pod borer, pod sucking bugs and foliage beetle for its efficacy. *Beauveria bassiana* belongs to the order *Hypocreales* and the family *Ophiocordycipitaceae* and its mode of action is argued to be the capacity of the fungi to destroy host cuticle proteins during germination of conidia. Also, *B. bassiana* produces toxic non-enzymatic compounds such as basianolidae and beauvericin that fasten infestation process by causing physiological alteration. Ba *et al.*, 2019 stated that *B. bassiana* can cause 100 % larval mortality in aphids and maruca pod borer and is also toxic to their eggs. It has also tested effective against *C. maculatus*.

Saranya et al., 2010 conducted an experiment to evaluate the efficacy of different entomopathogenic fungi against aphids. They used *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Verticillium lecanii*, *Hirsutella thompsonii* and *Cladosporium oxysporum* at six different concentration with highest been 10^8 spores / ml and being lowest 10^3 spores/ ml. They discovered that, decrease in concentration causes a corresponding decrease in mortality but all fungi that gave the high mortality percentage when used at the different concentration. *V. lecanii* and *H.thompsonii*, *B. bassiana*, *M. anisopliae* and *C. oxysporium* caused 100 %, 96.66%, 80.76 % and 77.5 % mortality after 7 days respectively. This proves that all the entomopathogenic fungi stated above can be used to control aphids since more than half of the aphid population was killed.

The antifeedant and pathogenicity of *Beauveria Bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* against adult beetle of *Ootheca mutabilis* using conidial suspension of four isolates of each pathogenic fungi (Ekesi, 2001). Isolate of *B. Bassiana* used were CPD 3, CPD 7, CPD 9 and CPD 10 and isolates of *M. anisopliae* used were CPD 4 and CPD 6. In the pathogenicity assay, he stated that

all the isolate were effective against the adult beetle but at different levels. For *B.bassiana*, CPD 3 and CPD 10 and for *M. anisopliae* CPD 6 were not effective against the beetles causing total mortality. In the antifeedant assay, he discovered that feeding was significantly reduced after two days after treatment application and this pattern continued until the seventh days of which all the beetles died.

Mehinto et al., 2020 explained that the virus maruca vitrata multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (MaviMNPV) was highly specific against maruca pod borer. This improves its effectiveness as a natural enemy against the maruca pod borer. The bacteria *Bacillus thuringiensis* is effective the major insect pests of cowpea. *Aspergillus flavus* have been proven to be effective some of the major insect pests such as foliage beetle. 100 % mortality was recorded after seven days of application at a concentration of 1×10^9 conidia / ml (Ekesi, 2001).

Parasitic wasps or parasitoids can also be used to major insect pests of cowpea. Ba et al., 2019 stated that parasitoid wasps' species in Africa are from the families *Eulophidae*, *Braconidae*, *Scelionidae*, *Icheumonidae*, *Pteromalidae*, *Chalcididae*, *Trichogrammatoidae* and *Tachinidae*. From the family *Tachinidae*, are the larval parasitoids *Theocarcelia incedens* and *Aplomya metallica*. Some Parasitoids are also *Phanerotoma leucobasis* and *Braunsia kriegei* parasite on both larvae and eggs of *M.vitrata* while *Trichogramma eldanae* is an egg parasitoid of *M.vitrata*.

Predators are also natural enemies that can directly feed on adult, larvae, pupa and eggs of insect pests to reduce their population either on the field or in store. Some examples of predators against the major insect pests include, hoverfly larvae, lace wings, ladybird beetle, assassin bugs and damsel bugs. Also, include mites, spider, ants and mantids. Some predators belonging to the family *mantidae* are *Polyspilota aeruginosa* and *Spodromantis lineolata*.

In the store, Even though, *C. maculatus* is subjected to high level of parasitism in nature little work have been done by researchers. Larval and pupal parasitoids of *C. maculatus* include *Dinarmus basalis* and *Eupelmus orientalis* and they feed on small larvae and pupa reducing their population and limiting damage caused. Also, Titouhi et al., 2012 stated that *Dinarmus* spp which belong to the order hymenoptera and family pteromalidae are effective parasitoids against *C. maculatus*. The main egg parasitoids of *C. maculatus* are the *Uscana* spp. *Uscana* spp include *Uscana lariophaga* and *Uscana mukerjii* that prevents eggs from hatching. There are predators that feed on *C. maculatus* examples are *Cheyletus eruditus* and *Anisopteromalus calandrae*. There are also a number of entomopathogenic fungi and bacteria of *C. maculatus*. Naba et al., 2012 established the ability of *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* to control *C. maculatus* reducing the level of damage caused.

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHOD

For the purpose of this review, all information used were from articles retrieved online from various academic platforms such as Academia, Google scholar, Science direct and annual review of entomology. The plates used to represent give a pictorial image of the various insects and their lifecycle were retrieved online using the search engine google chrome. Data represented in both tabular form and graphical form were secondary data obtained from the various academic articles used for the review. Therefore, no further analysis of data using statistical software was done since all data used were analyzed by the various authors.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

Damages and economic losses incurred by farmers as a result of insect pest activities have necessitated their control. Insect pests causes huge economic losses which greatly hampers the production of cowpea. Therefore, various control measures have been adopted and used to curtail their level of infestation. Also, fields such as biological control, chemical control and cultural practices have all been explored to manage insect pests both on the field and in store.

The use of synthetic insecticides such as cypermethrin, alphaeypermethrin, deltamethrin and lambdacyhalothrin based synthetic pyrethoids have all been evaluated against the major insect pests of cowpea. Its usage against insect pests is considered as the mainstay of agriculture since it gives forth quick and effective control of these insect pests. Oyewale et al., 2013 stated that, chemicals used to control insect pests of cowpea are mostly from four main classes. Which are organophosphates, organochlorides, carbamates and pyrethoids. They further emphasized the importance of synthetic insecticide by concluding that, complete crop failure can occur when improved varieties are grown without at least one round of insecticidal spray to control insect pest.

The efficacy of Lamba-cyhalothrin against major insect pests of cowpea was evaluated by Badii et al., 2013. They used six different formulation of lambda-cyhalothrin against maruca pod borer, aphids, thrips and pod sucking bugs to evaluate the most effective. Clear, controller-super, CW-lambda, Kombat, Lambda-super, Zap were the formulations of Lambda-cyhalothrin used with water been the control treatment. Using the rate 25l/ha, treatment were applied at three spraying times which are once during the vegetative stage, flowering stage and podding stage.

Table 3. Mean number of insect pests and average yield of grains

Treatment	Mean of thrips infestation	Mean number of PSBs per 5m row	Proportion (%) of shriveled pods	Mean yield of grain Kg/ha	Average Mean number of <i>M.vitrata</i> larvae on flowers and pods
Control	4.4	39.4	39.4	324.0	5.2
Clear	0.9	2.3	10.0	645.4	0.73
Controller-super	1.75	3.0	8.8	605.0	0.6
CW-lambda	0.9	1.7	6.6	988.5	0.415
Kombat	1.0	2.3	12,6	668.0	0.2
Lambda-super	0.5	1.9	6.0	1189.1	0.115
Zap	1.0	2.3	12.4	665.3	0.985

Badii *et al.*, 2013

They observed that among the different formulation, the plots treated with lambda-super gave better results than the other plots although all the formulations were effective. Since for all the parameters significantly better results were obtained for the treated plots. For the control of thrips, Zap and kombat gave the same level of control as well as clear and CW-lambda also gave the same level of control. The most effective was Lambda-super and the least effective among the formulations for controlling thrips was controller-super. For yield of grain, lambda-super gave the highest yield (1189.1 Kg/ha) which is significantly higher (3.67 fold more) than the yield of the control plot (324 Kg/ha). The lowest mean number of pod sucking bugs was obtained for the plot treated with CW-lambda formulation. Results presented in figure 19 is the average control of the means of number of *M.vitrata* larvae found on the flower and pods. For the mean number of larvae found on the flower all the treatment were significant although the highest result was recorded for

the plots sprayed with lambda-super and komba with lowest results obtained for zap treated plots. For the mean number of larvae found in the pods, the highest control was observed for lambda-super treated plots and lowest for zap treated plots.

Opolot et al., 2005 stated that cypermethrin is effective against flower bud thrips because spraying of cowpea plants with cypermethrin significantly reduced its infestation level. Spraying was done at budding and flowering stages of the crop. Furthermore, they concluded that spraying five times with cypermethrin not only control thrips but also pod sucking bugs, legume pod borer and cowpea beetle but does not prevent the total transfer of cowpea beetle to storage.

Ba et al., 2019 explained that, a great portion of chemicals such as DDT used to control the legume pod-borer are not recently. But, there are a number found to be effective against the legume pod-borer *M. vitrata* such as organophosphate, lambda-cyhalothrin, deltamethrin and cypermethrin. They also stated that in Nigeria, the most effective approach against *M. vitrata* is spraying twice with lambda-cyhalothrin or cypermethrin combined with dimethoate.

According to Ganapathy (2010), controlling of the major insect pests of cowpea can be done using four high volume spray of cypermethrin at a concentration of 0.008 %. The spraying times is argued on where initial flowering, 50 % flowering, 100 % flowering and 100 % pod setting.

Sharma et al., 1998 also explained that, spraying twice with endosulfan applied 35 days after planting at weekly intervals, one spray of cypermethrin, cyhalothrin, bipenthrin and in combination with dimethoate or two applications of cypermethrin and dimethoate at 10 days intervals beginning at bud formation can be used to control the major pests of cowpea on the field.

In store, most synthetic insecticide such as fumigants and emulsifiers have also been tested against *C.maculatus*. For instance, phosphine, methyl bromide, delta methrin and Malathion have been evaluated for its efficacy against *C.maculatus* (Sanon et al., 2018). Most farmers in Ghana also use agrochemicals such as Malathion, perfekthion 20 EC, atelic and cymbush to control *C. maculatus* (Tweneboah, 2000).

Botanicals

The use of plant materials to control insect pest's populations on cowpea of agricultural is considered as a promising alternative to synthetic insecticide (Idoko et al., 2018; Sanon et al., 2018). Plants material such as powders, essential oils and extracts may produce volatile chemicals that may be toxic or repel the major insect pests of cowpea reducing the damages incurred during production or in store. While as, others produce secondary metabolites that directly affect development and reproduction of the major insect pests. Botanicals are also relatively harmless to non- target organisms, biodegradable, cheaper, environmentally friendly and low development of resistance.

Oparaeke (2006) explained that, crude extracts from plants (powder, water extracts, oils and wood ash) have been widely used by farmers to control the major insect pests of cowpea since different active ingredients which confer for different pesticidal such as attractants and oviposition deterrents activity have been observed. Also, Manzoor et al., 2011 explained that, a variety of properties have been shown by plants extract which includes, insecticide activity, repellency to pests, antifeedants effects, insect growth regulation, toxicity to other biological pests such as nematodes, mites, fungi and bacterial. These properties increase the potential of plant extracts in controlling these major insect pests of cowpea both on the field and in store.

On the field, a range of botanicals have tested and its efficacy in managing the major insect pests have established. For instance, *Piper guineense*, *Artocarpus altilis*, *Aframomum melegueta*, *Carica papaya* and neem- based preparations have been tested against insect pests of cowpea ranging from pre flowering insects to podding insects pest. Ganapathy, 2010 explained that some extracts act as antifeedant preventing their infestation. Plants extracts include extracts from neem seed kernels and chilli fruits which showed high deterrent effects against these major insect pests on the field when sprayed or when the applied as dust in its dried form around the cowpea plants significantly reduced the infestation of the legume pod borer. This significantly increased the grain yield of cowpea obtained. This was confirmed when different concentration of emulsifiable concentrate (5 %, 10% and 20 %) was used against *M. vitrata* and high degree of its toxic effects was observed (Jackai and Oyediran, 19991).

Azadirachta occidentale has been used to control insect pests on many economically important crops in different parts of the world. It has been commercialized for over twenty years now with its usage widely across the world for many different insect pests on many economically important crops. Its efficacious effect against the major insect pests of cowpea was evaluated by many researchers including Badii et al., 2008, Elango et al., 2009, Degri et al., 2013 and Okolo and Oyewale, 2019. Oyewale et al., 2013 suggested that, admixing neem oil to cowpea at a rate of 2-5ml/kg can effectively control cowpea weevil for up to 8 months with damages less than 15 %. Also, the efficacy of neem against aphids was shown by Elango et al, 2009 by proving that, 54.4 % and 51.1 % mortality was caused when extracts from its leaves at 1000 ppm(0.02%) and its seed kernel 5 % was sprayed and recorded after 48 hours. This also shows that, there will be an increase in mortality will be observed when concentration is increased to significantly control aphids. Furthermore, the efficacy of extracts from the seeds and leaves of neem against pod sucking bug

complex have been established even though the seed extract gave better results than the extract from the leaves (Okolo and Oyewole, 2019).

The potential of *Azadirachta indica*, *Chromolaena odorata* and *Ricinus communis* as an insecticide against pod sucking bug complex (*Anoplocnemis* spp, *Riptortus* spp, *Clavigralla* spp and *Nezara viridula*) using its leaf extract have been established (Degri et al., 2013). They observed that, even though all three species were effective against the pod sucking bugs, *Ricinus communis* was relatively less effective than *A. Indica* and *C. Odorata*. This was correlated from the results obtained from the various plots sprayed with *A. Indica*, *C. Odorata*, *R. Communis* and water as control using the yield, number of pods and weight of pods. With the number of pods and weight of the pods observed, *Azadirachta indica* and *Chromolaena odorata* had 23-25 pods and 14-15 g, *R. Communis* had 21 pods and 13 g with the control plots gave 16 pods and 9 g respectively. Consequently, the grain yield obtained from plots sprayed with *A. Indica* and *C. Odorata* were four times that of the control well as *R. Communis* was three times more than the yield obtained from the control plots. Also, the spraying of the plots was done fortnightly beginning on the on-set of pods using 5% w/v concentration of leaf extract.

The bioefficacy of six different insecticide was evaluated against aphids using reduction in population after treatment application and economic benefits. They used Jhomol, Neem extract, Cannabis extract which are botanicals (Biopesticide) at a concentration of 125 ml/L. They included synthetic insecticide Chloropyrifus 50 % EC and Cypermethrin 5 % at a dose of 2ml/L to compare the efficiency of the botanicals against it. As shown in the figure 2, neem extract and chloropyriphos 50 % and cypermethrin 5% EC gave the highest percentage of aphid reduction

after their application well as the lowest aphid reduction percentage was recorded for plots sprayed with cannabis extract.

Figure 2. Effects of different sprays of different insecticides on percent reduction in aphid over control.

Source. Dhakal et al., 2019

In Ghana, Badii et al., 2008 conducted a field experiment to evaluate the efficacy of neem seed extract against the major insect pests of cowpea (Aphids, thrips, maruca pod borer and pod sucking bugs complex). For the neem seed extracts of 5%, 10%, 20% concentration were sprayed using the knapsack sprayer with water been the control treatment. Data collection for aphid incidence and severity was done 25 and 44 days after planting using a scoring scale of 0-9 with 0 representing 0 aphids, 1 representing 1-4 aphids, 3 representing 5-20 aphids, 5 representing 21-100 aphids, 7 representing 101-500 aphids and 9 represents over 500 aphids per subplot according to the scale proposed by Jackie and Singh, 1988. Infestation of thrips was assessed between flower bud initiation and 50 % podding stage by counting the number of nymphs and adults on the plant. For the assessment of pod borer infestation, ten flowers from each subplot were picked randomly and

kept in vials with 50 % ethanol and this was done between 50 % flowering and first pod maturity.

For the pod sucking bugs evaluation, visual observation was used to count their abundance.

They observed that all the treatment applied were effective against the major insect pests of cowpea when the level of infestation were significantly lower than the control. This can be correlated to the capacity of the active ingredients to acts as phagoterents, growth regulators, repellent, disruptive effects and olfactory. They observed the as the concentration of the neem seed extract increases, its disruptive effect increases. Also, throughout all the parameters used, the extract of 20 % concentration gave better results significantly than the others. The highest yield was recorded from the plot sprayed with 20 % NSE extract reducing significantly as the concentration reduces. They explained that, as the concentration of the neem extract increases its effect also increases giving forth better results.

Table 4. Mean score of the major pest of cowpea and yield obtained.

Treatment	% of plants infested by aphids	Mean aphid score	Mean number of thrips per racema	Mean number of thrips per flower	Proportion (%) of flower infested by Maruca pod borer	Proportion (%) of damage pods by maruca pod borer
Control	36.6	3.0	57.2	58.6	72.5	72.8
5 % NSE	10.5	2.2	35.3	37.0	47.5	44.1
10 % NSE	6.7	1.7	27.5	20.0	38.7	33.6
15 % NSE	6.3	1.4	19.5	12.5	23.7	13.7
20 % NSE	5.5	1.1	14.5	9.5	20.0	12.2

Table 5. Mean score of major cowpea pest and yield obtained.

Treatment	Mean number of <i>R.dentipes</i> per 5 m row of cowpea	Mean number of <i>C.tomentosicollis</i> per 5 m row of cowpea	Mean number of <i>A. curvipes</i> per 5 m row of cowpea	Mean number of <i>N. viridia</i> per 5m row of cowpea	Proportion of shriveled pods (%)	Mean yield
Control	9.3	7.5	6.2	5.5	85.4	203.3
5 % NSE	6.0	4.0	4.0	3.8	67.7	408.0
10 % NSE	4.8	4.0	3.0	2.2	28.0	709.0
15 % NSE	4.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	11.2	1455.5
20 % NSE	3.6	2.8	2.2	2.0	10.5	1471.5

As represented in table 4 and table 5, the mean aphid score reduced as the concentration increases. Implying that less aphid were recorded on plots with high concentration of neem extract. Low number of infested plants was also recorded on plots treated with high concentration of neem extract. Also, similar results were obtained for the mean infestation score as well as yield obtained went down the same pattern. Therefore, it can be concluded that, the efficacy of neem extract against cowpea insect pest is directly related to the concentration of the neem extract.

Oparaeke (2006) established the efficacy of piper guineese against flower bud thrips by evaluating the pod density per plant on different plots sprayed with 5 %, 10 % and 20 % (w/v) extract of the botanical. He then discovered that, the pod density per plant was significantly high for the plots sprayed with 10 % and 20 % extract of piper guineese at a spraying time of two, four and six weekly interval starting from flower bud formation at a rate of 150 l/ ha. This is because, flower

bud thrip infestation pressure was reduced in these plots when compared with those sprayed with 5 % extract concentration.

The effect of some cereal (sorghum, pearl millet and maize) and legume (Cowpea and soyabean) extract against pod sucking bugs through the inhibition of protease enzyme activity was investigated (Taiwo et al., 2016). They discovered that, the legumes were more effective in controlling the pod sucking bug complex than the cereals by reducing the damage incurred as a result of their infestation. *Azadirachta indica* seed extract is also known to be effective against the foliage beetls particularly *O. mutabilis*.

Furthermore, in the store various botanicals have also been tested against *C. maculatus* since it is the major insect pest of cowpea during storage. Essential oils from plants are mostly used in protecting cowpea grains during storage since it can be used as both contact and synthetic insecticide against stored insect pest particularly *C. maculatus* which is the major pest in store (Osekere, 1998; Ogboannna et al., 2016; Oliveria et al., 2018). The mode of action has been argued as to be very diverse ranging from physical through repellency action to chemical toxicity to all stages of insect development (Osekere, 1998; Ogboannna et al., 2016; Oliveria et al., 2018). The oils enters the spiracle and trachea of *C. maculatus* causing asphyxiation and therefore death. They also hypothesis that occlusion effect by some oils is the reason for their ovicidal and larval effects. It mode of action as ovicide can be related to infiltrating under the opercium and blocking respiration or disrupt the water balance of eggs and developing embryos (Oskere, 1998).

Brito et al., 2006 cited in Oliveria et al., 2018 evaluated, the toxicity of essential oils from *Eucalyptus* spp. On *C. maculatus* and observed reduction in lethal time and lethal concentration at 50 with increase in exposure time and doses. The efficacy of essential oil also from thymus

persicus against *C. maculatus* was investigated by Saroukolai et al., 2013. They discovered that over 88 % mortality was recorded when *C. maculatus* was exposed for 24 hours to 9.8 µl/ L air.

In addition, the essential oil of plants from the citrus genus and its components have also shown insecticidal activity against *C. maculatus* (Dutra et al., 2016 cited in Oliveria et al., 2018). In addition to these essential oils, Nwankwo et al., (2009) proved that, *Azadirachta Indica* seed oil cause increase in mortality leading to reduction in the number of eggs laid and therefore emergence and number of holed cowpea seeds. Azadirachtin is the active ingredient of neem extracts and it acts as an anti-ovipositant, adulticide and larvicide which has been well established for the control of *C. maculatus*. Oliveria et al., 2018, investigated the repellency potential of essential oils from *Schinus terebinfolius*, *Piper aduncum*, *Syzygium aromaticum*, *piper hispidinervum*, *Cymbopogon citratus* and *Cinnamomum zeylani*. They confirmed that among the selected plants, *S. aromaticum* and *P. hispidnervum* has the potential to repel *C. maculatus*. They then used gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometer to find out its active ingredients which were safrole and eugenol respectively.

The use of dried powders from plants has also been used to analyze to establish its efficacy by many researchers. Dried powder of *Zingiber officinale* was used by Ogbonna et al., 2016 to evaluate its efficacy against *C. maculatus*. They discovered that, it exhibits various levels of toxicity by acting as an anti-feedant. Also the higher the concentration, the more significant its efficacy. This agrees with the research done by Bamphitlhi et al., 2014 on reproduction and damage of *C. maculatus* using garlic, peppermint and chilies. They discovered that chilies and garlic had negative effects on the reproduction and damage since it substantially increases mortality but less

effect was recorded for peppermint. The effectivity of ashes and powders of some plants was also established by some researchers.

This is in accordance with the finding of Dari, 2008, who proved that wood ash from mahogany (*Khaya senegalensis*) and dried powdered orange peel can remarkably control *C. maculatus* during the first six months of storing cowpea without compromising its' viability and quality. Idoko et al., 2018, showed that the powder of both ripped and unripe pawpaw seeds can act as an insecticide against *C. maculatus*. When 0.8 g/ 20 kg of concentration was used for both powder of ripped and unripe pawpaw seeds, 83.3 % and 100 % mortality was recorded respectively. A plausible explanation for the difference in mortality can be attributed to the converting of the insecticidal chemicals during the ripening process to less harmful ones. Extracts from *Hemizygia welwitschii* using different solvent (hexane, acetone and methanol) was also tested, and the results proved that all the solvent were effective against *C. maculatus* at the highest dosage 10g/kg (Fotso et al., 2019). They furthermore concluded that, the higher the concentration and exposure time, the more effective the control. This is concordance with findings of other researchers (Bamphitlhi et al., 2014; Ogonna et al., 2016; Nwankwo et al., 2009).

Cultural control

Cultural control is the measure of controlling pest and disease of crops by manipulating the environment within which the crop is grown or stored. Its measures are considered preventive rather than curative although it is the oldest control measure. It is also argued that, control measures are variable since its results are dependent on environmental conditions. Measures adopted are the use of resistant varieties, manipulating of planting date and spacing, the use of trap crops and traps, harvesting time, farm hygiene and type of storage facility adopted.

The effect manipulation of planting dates and spacing has been established to some extent to affect or influence the level of insect pest infestation on the field. Sowing of cowpea early enable plants to escape most field insect pests attack and help develop pseudo resistance. Sharma and Ortiz (2002) explained that early sowing of cowpea leads to variation in temperature, photoperiod and other environmental conditions that affect establishment of insect pests on hosts and this phenomenon is known as pseudo resistance or false resistance. Spacing affects the plant density which in turn have as effect on the insect pest population on the field. Sharma, 1998 stated that early sowing of cowpea enables plant begin flowering before peaking of aphid population using they are most susceptible during the flowering stage to aphids. Also, dense crop canopy of cowpea plant by using high sowing rate help to deter aphid landing therefore reducing their population. Ba et al, 2019 also concluded that planting early significantly reduced infestation of insect pests on the field. Also, an experiment conducted by Karungi *et al.*, 2000a proved that planting on the onset of rains at a density of 30 cm by 20 cm or 60 cm by 20 cm which gives a plant population of 183.333 plants/ ha and 100.000 plants/ha was better when assessed against 90 cm by 20 cm and 120 cm by 20 cm that plant population of 66.667 plants/ha and 50.00 plants/ ha respectively for effect caused by cowpea insect pests. They related this to the interference of visual stimulation of aphids caused by the dense crop population leading to reduced colonization and fecundity. It also known that early planting of cowpea helps it to escape periods of heavy infestation. Contrary to their finding, Kanteh et al., (2014) stated that planting density of 50 cm by 30 cm was most appropriate for controlling aphids as well as foliage beetle.

Karungi et al., 2000b discovered that, the interaction between type of cultivar planted, plant density and spray schedule influence infestation of aphids and pod sucking bugs. They stated, the effect of one factor was influenced by the other two factors but for thrips infestation. They are

influences by higher temperature despite the availability of susceptible cowpea plants since they are susceptible to high temperature. They also stated that for the level of infestation by thrips, the three factors have little or no effect. They also discovered that, the management of the cowpea major pests in combination with a plant density of 30 cm by 20 cm performed better than that of 60 cm by 20 cm in terms of marginal returns and thus grain yield. Also, semi-erect varieties and erect varieties respond positively to the management of high insect pest population

Cowpea is mostly intercropped with cereals such as maize, sorghum, millet although direct benefits are not derived but rather there can be competition for nutrient and light. Nevertheless, the micro climate created is argued to reduce pest complex since it modifies the environment making it unfavorable for their establishment. Modification of the environment results from the increase of crop diversify on the field, lower temperature, higher relative humidity and reduced light transmission or penetration into canopy formed by crop.

Also, results obtained from intercropping cowpea with other crops is said to be variable and dependent on environmental conditions as well as other control measure adopted. This can be associated to the increase on the level of infestation by some insect pests. Mweke et al., 2020 stated that intercropping of cowpea alone does not control field insect of cowpea particularly aphids. A more effective control measure is the combination of intercropping with entomopathogenic fungi. Cowpea was intercropped with maize and *Metarhizium anisopliae* ICIPE 62 and this gave a significantly lower aphid infestation level.

Intercropping of cowpea with other compatible crops is widely used in Ghana since most cowpea production in Ghana is done on a subsistence level. Intercropping of cowpea with other crops such as maize, sorghum, cassava and millet results in crop diversity, lower temperature,

higher relative humidity and reduced light transmission or penetration into canopy formed by crop. Results obtained from intercropping cowpea with other crops is said to be variable and dependent on environmental conditions as well as other control measure adopted. This can be associated to the increase on the level of infestation by some insect pests.

This agrees with the results obtained by Kampala et al, 1999 that, intercropping cowpea with sorghum alone did not provide sufficient control against cowpea pests particularly aphids well as combining intercropping with foliar and seed dressing insecticide greatly increased yields. Gianessi (2013) also reported that intercropping of cowpea controlled aphids but had no effect on thrips, maruca pod borer and pod-sucking bugs because high plant density and early infestation reduces aphid infestation. Cited in Kusi *et al.*, 2019, Matteson 1982 said that intercropping cowpea with maize reduces the population of thrips on the field. Sharma, 1998 stated that intercropping with maize lead to build up pod borer population but planting cowpea 12 weeks after planting maize reduces the pod borer population and also intercropping cowpea with sorghum and maize as maize-cowpea-sorghum also helps with reducing of insect pests on the field.

The use of trap crops and insect traps to attract cowpea insect pests on the field. Trap crops are crops planted in at specific parts of the field to attract insect pest and prevent or minimize their damage on target crops. After insect pests infest trap crops, they are then easily controlled since they are concentrated on the trap crops. Sharma, 1998 stated that *crotalaria spp* can be used as trap crops of maruca pod borer. This attracts the female moths to deposit their eggs on them when the trap crops are planted early on the field bunds. Also when insect traps such as pheromone traps are used, level of infestation of cowpea insect pests are reduced. Ba et al., 2019 used pheromone traps of EE10, 12-16: Ald and EE10, 12-16: OH as major and minor components respectively and a

third component being (E)-10 hexadecenal (E10-16: ALD) was successful when used as lure and kill trap against maruca pod borer. Cited by Ba *et al.*, 2019, the most effective lure and kill trap against maruca pod borer was a water trap made from 5 l plastic jerry-can placed at 120 cm height with lure attracting for 2 weeks (Downham *et al.*, 2004). The lure and trap such as yellow sticky trap and protein bait can also be used for monitoring of cowpea insect pests on the field.

Weed control, good farm hygiene and removal of alternate host plants. Cowpea insect pests have sources that serve as alternate host that they infest and harbor to over season when cowpea is out of season. Kusi *et al.*, 2019 discussed that most resource poor farmers combine good farm conditions such as regular weed control measures to help minimize insect pests' infestation on the field. Also, pod sucking bugs can be hand-picked and killed under low infestation and small plots. To control foliage and aphids infestation on the field, weeding twice at three and six weeks after planting reduces their infestation (Kanteh 2014).

Harvesting of pods should be done at the appropriate time and frequency to reduce or prevent initial infestation of the field since *C. maculatus* is a field-to-store pest (Chelav *et al.*, 2013; Fatima *et al.*, 2016). That is, harvesting of pods should be done before they completely dry and split open. This significantly reduces substantial damage or prevent infestation of the produce since the adult female first lays its eggs on drying pods on the field prior to harvesting and into store after harvesting. Also, sorting of grains should be done before storage to remove field infested grains from the stock and frequent inspection of stored grains should also be carried out. In stores, the racks used, corners and floors must be kept clean during storage and disinfested prior to storage.

The adoption of hermetic storage technology for storing cowpea also helps since the type of storage structure influences the level of infestation and thus level of damage incurred. Hermetic storage is

a chemical-free and cost-effective way of controlling insect during storage to maintain grain quality and therefore its adoption can be very sustainable in Africa (Aboagy *et al.*, 2017). Hermetic storage principally occurs in controlled environment which continuously depletes oxygen levels and simultaneously increases carbon dioxide as a result of respiratory activities. The research on hermetic storage technology has led to the development of triple bagging technology with PICS (Purdue improved cowpea storage) bags (Dari, 2008; Aboagye *et al.*, 2017). This technology was developed by Purdue University in collaboration with Africa researchers and is widely used as an alternative to synthetic insecticide and metal silos. A PICS bag is composed of three layers: two inner layers of high density polyethylene and an outer layer of ordinary woven polypropylene. This works by suffocating adult and larvae to death and can protect grains up to three months without compromising its quality (Dari, 2008).

Biological control

There is a wide range of natural enemies against the major insect pest of cowpea. Natural enemies can be classified into three groups which are predators, parasitoids and entomopathogens. These groups of natural enemies can be used both on the field, in store and in the laboratory to control pests while maintaining biodiversity and reducing production cost.

Entomopathogenic organisms are fungi, bacteria, protozoa and viruses. To some extent, entomopathogenic organisms have been tested against insect pests. Ganapathy (2010) argued that, the rate or percentage of control of insect pests using pathogens can be said to be 30 %. A number of these entomopathogenic organisms have been tested and found effective against the major insect pests of cowpea.

The most common entopathogenic fungi used against most of the major insect pest of cowpea is *Beauveria Bassiana*. It has been tested against aphids, maruca pod borer, pod sucking bugs and foliage beetle for its efficacy. *Beauveria bassiana* belongs to the order *Hypocreales* and the family *Ophiocordycipitaceae* and its mode of action is argued to be the capacity of the fungi to destroy host cuticle proteins during germination of conidia. Also, *B. bassiana* produces toxic non-enzymatic compounds such as basianolidae and beauvericin that fasten infestation process by causing physiological alteration. Ba *et al.*, 2019 stated that *B. bassiana* can cause 100 % larval mortality in aphids and maruca pod borer and is also toxic to their eggs. It has also tested effective against *C. maculatus*.

Saranya et al., 2010 conducted an experiment to evaluate the efficacy of different entomopathogenic fungi against aphids. They used *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Verticillium lecanii*, *Hirsutella thompsonii* and *Cladosporium oxysporum* at six different concentration with highest been 10^8 spores / ml and being lowest 10^3 spores/ ml. They discovered that, decrease in concentration causes a corresponding decrease in mortality but all fungi that gave the high mortality percentage when used at the different concentration. *V. lecanii* and *H.thompsonii*, *B. bassiana*, *M. anisopliae* and *C. oxysporium* caused 100 %, 96.66%, 80.76 % and 77.5 % mortality after 7 days respectively. This proves that all the entomopathogenic fungi stated above can be used to control aphids since more than half of the aphid population was killed.

The antifeedant and pathogenicity of *Beauveria Bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* against adult beetle of *Ootheca mutabilis* using conidial suspension of four isolates of each pathogenic fungi (Ekesi, 2001). Isolate of *B. Bassiana* used were CPD 3, CPD 7, CPD 9 and CPD 10 and isolates of *M. anisopliae* used were CPD 4 and CPD 6. In the pathogenicity assay, he stated that

all the isolate were effective against the adult beetle but at different levels. For *B.bassiana*, CPD 3 and CPD 10 and for *M. anisopliae* CPD 6 were not effective against the beetles causing total mortality. In the antifeedant assay, he discovered that feeding was significantly reduced after two days after treatment application and this pattern continued until the seventh days of which all the beetles died.

Mehinto et al., 2020 explained that the virus maruca vitrata multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (MaviMNPV) was highly specific against maruca pod borer. This improves its effectiveness as a natural enemy against the maruca pod borer. The bacteria *Bacillus thuringiensis* is effective the major insect pests of cowpea. *Aspergillus flavus* have been proven to be effective some of the major insect pests such as foliage beetle. 100 % mortality was recorded after seven days of application at a concentration of 1×10^9 conidia / ml (Ekesi, 2001).

Parasitic wasps or parasitoids can also be used to major insect pests of cowpea. Ba et al., 2019 stated that parasitoid wasps' species in Africa are from the families *Eulophidae*, *Braconidae*, *Scelionidae*, *Icheumonidae*, *Pteromalidae*, *Chalcididae*, *Trichogrammatoidae* and *Tachinidae*. From the family *Tachinidae*, are the larval parasitoids *Theocarcelia incedens* and *Aplomya metallica*. Some Parasitoids are also *Phanerotoma leucobasis* and *Braunsia kriegei* parasite on both larvae and eggs of *M.vitrata* while *Trichogramma eldanae* is an egg parasitoid of *M.vitrata*.

Predators are also natural enemies that can directly feed on adult, larvae, pupa and eggs of insect pests to reduce their population either on the field or in store. Some examples of predators against the major insect pests include, hoverfly larvae, lace wings, ladybird beetle, assassin bugs and damsel bugs. Also, include mites, spider, ants and mantids. Some predators belonging to the family *mantidae* are *Polyspilota aeruginosa* and *Spodromantis lineolata*.

In the store, Even though, *C. maculatus* is subjected to high level of parasitism in nature little work have been done by researchers. Larval and pupal parasitoids of *C. maculatus* include *Dinarmus basalis* and *Eupelmus orientalis* and they feed on small larvae and pupa reducing their population and limiting damage caused. Also, Titouhi et al., 2012 stated that *Dinarmus* spp which belong to the order hymenoptera and family pteromalidae are effective parasitoids against *C. maculatus*. The main egg parasitoids of *C. maculatus* are the *Uscana* spp. *Uscana* spp include *Uscana lariophaga* and *Uscana mukerjii* that prevents eggs from hatching. There are predators that feed on *C. maculatus* examples are *cheyletus eruditus* and *Anisopteromalus calandrae*. There are also a number of entomopathogenic fungi and bacteria of *C. maculatus*. Naba et al., 2012 established the ability of *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* to control *C. maculatus* reducing the level of damage caused.

Host plant resistance

The relative amount of heritable qualities possessed by a plant or its material an example being its seeds which influences the extent to which damages are caused by an insect is known as host plant resistance (Ahmed and Yusuf, 2007). Host plant resistance is said to be an effective, economic, socially acceptable and environmentally friendly method of controlling insect pests (Sharma and Ortiz, 2002). It does not require some special level of know-how or application techniques and no cash investment making it most appropriate and sustainability to most farmers specifically resource poor farmers. Sharma and Ortiz (2002) explained that Host plant resistance is the adaptive and heritable feature of plants against insect pests that enable the plant to avoid or inhibit host selection, oviposition, feeding of insects on them. It also reduces or limits insect's survival

and development on them as well as ability to recover or tolerant damage or injury caused by these insect pests.

Expression of resistance by plants is dependent on some factors mainly insect density and environmental conditions. Host plant resistance can be derived from physiochemical characteristics of plants which influences the behavior and biology of insects. For instance a number of seeds are said to be resistant to *C. maculatus* based on the possession of some chemicals that inhibit *C. maculatus* establishment on them. Chemical include, Trypsin inhibitors, Tannins, chitinases, insecticide lentins and Beta-1, 3- glucanases with a typical example been the possession of Alpha-amylase inhibitors by *Phaseolus vulgaris* prevents the development of *C. maculatus* on its seeds. Plant resistance is relative since the level of resistance is expressed in relation to other plants of the same species when grown under similar environmental conditions. It is expressed in terms of damage and injury incurred by plants during infestation of insect pests and the level of tolerance and recovery exhibited by the resistant genotypes.

Some genotypes and cultivar are known to have some level of tolerance or resistance against a number of cowpea insect pests but usually not all cowpea insect pests. It is known that the only cultivar highly resistant against *M. vitrata* is the wild vigna *Vigna vexilata* (Ba *et al.*, 2019; Mehinto *et al.*, 2020). Kusi *et al.*, 2019 conducted an experiment in the sudan and guinea savannah zones of Ghana located in the northern parts of the country to assess the tolerance level of different cultivars in combination with insecticide spraying times. IT99K-573-1-1 (resistant to striga, drought and macrophomina with a potential yield of 2.4 tons/ha), IT99K-573-2-1 (striga resistant, drought and macrophomina tolerant amd known as in Ghana as wangkae and also has aphid resistant gene), sonogotra (low tolerance to macrophomina and resistant to striga), Padituga

(drought and macrophomina tolerant), Bawutuwuta (striga tolerant with moderate to low resistance to insect pests and disease and a farmer's cultivar widely grown in the region were the genotypes they assessed. They discovered that Bawutuwuta, Songota, IT99K-573-1-1, IT99K-573-2-1 were tolerant to thrips because despite the high level of thrip infestation, relatively high yield were obtained as a result of quick replacement of trip-damaged or abscised flower.

The genotypes VITA 7, IT84S-2246 and TVx3236 were moderately resistant to aphids well as thrips. Therefore, two insecticide spray of lambda-cyhalothrin and dimethoate at a rate of 17 + 35 g ai/L (Afun et al., 1991). The genotypes TVu's 59, TVu's 123 and VITA-3 are resistant to leafhopper, TVu's 1509, TVu's 2870, TVu's 6507 and TVu's 7133 resistant to flower bud thrips and TVu's 946 and VITA-5 are resistant to maruca pod borer (Singh and Allen, 1980). Oparaeke et al., (2006) stated that, the genotypes TVu59, TVu 123, VITA-1 and VITA-3 were resistant to the infestation of leafhopper.

This was also confirmed by Abudulai et al., 2017 when they reported that genotype IT99K-573-2-1 and IT99K-573-1-1 were less susceptible to most economic pest of cowpea (Kusi et al., 2019). Kusi et al (2019) again stated that, the different genotypes exhibited different level of resistance against the pod sucking bugs while producing appreciable yield. The cultivar Zaayura which is widely cultivated in the northern region of Ghana as it has high resistance against aphids (Wahaga, 2019).

Also, varieties that produce protease inhibitors should be adopted and planted to minimize the effects of pod sucking bugs infestation since protease is an enzyme produced by the bugs during feeding. This results in tissue damage because it is a digestive enzyme that breakdown cells in the pod tissue for the absorption of nutrients. The effect of protease production of plants was

established by Taiwo et al. (2016) and they also investigated the effect and production of protease inhibitors by some cereal (sorghum, pearl millet and maize) and legume (Cowpea and soyabean) to minimize pod sucking bugs infestation effects. They therefore concluded that the legumes were more effective than the cereals and thus varieties that produce high levels of protease inhibitors should be used for cultivation.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

Individually, the different control measure cannot provide the desired level of satisfaction in controlling the major insect pests. Also, there disadvantages associated with the use of only one control measure making it necessary to integrate different control measure to successfully control these major insect pests. The integration of the different compatible control measure is known as integrated pest management (IPM). IPM is known to be a broad-based approach that integrate different control practices for a more economic, safe and sustainable method of suppression pest population. IPM aims to prevent insect pest or maintain them below the economic injury level with the least disruption to the agro-ecosystem and natural ecosystem while achieving appreciable yields of agricultural produce.

Different control tactics from cultural, chemical, biological and host plant resistance can adopted and integrated. For instance, results obtained from intercropping cowpea with other crops is said to be variable and dependent on environmental conditions as well as other control measure adopted. This can be associated to the controversy in the results obtained from different research done to establish its effect on the level of infestation by these major insect pests of cowpea.

Kusi *et al*, 2019 analyzed that, the integration of some resistant cultivar with appropriate insecticide spraying time was very effective in the controlling of the major insect pests (Aphids, maruca pod borer, thrips, pod sucking bugs) on the field. They also stated that, the spraying times most cost effective and possess less adverse effect are spraying at flower bud initiation, 50 % flowering stage and 50 % podding stage. This significantly reduce pest infestation while cowpea are able to produce high yield of quality grains. Also they concluded that, although different level

of responses of the cultivar to the major insect pests infestation level were observed, the management of these major insect pests requires the inclusion of minimal insecticide application.

It was noticed that in the experiment conducted by Mehinto *et al.*, 2020 that, the highest grain yield obtained was as a result of controlling these major insect pests using combined mixture of *Beauveria bassiana* and neem oil. Again, the result obtained from Karungi *et al* (2000b) experiment proves that integrating planting density and planting time with accurate spraying time gave very high yield. They therefore concluded that, planting cowpea at the on-set of the raining season at a density of either 30 cm by 20 cm and 60 cm by 20 cm combined with spraying once at budding, flowering and podding is the most appropriate for controlling these major insect pests.

Opolot *et al.*, 2006 also stated that integrating cypermethrin with tobacco gave better results of controlling major field insect pests of cowpea by applying tobacco at podding and cypermethrin at the other stages.

Also, integrating late planting with a planting density of 50 cm by 30 cm and spraying with chlorpyrifos 70ml/ gallon or dimethoate and cypermethrin 100 ml/14 l and hand picking and ploughing soils give the most appropriate method of controlling foliage beetle *O.mutabilis* (Kanteh 2013).

Furthermore, there are disadvantages associated with the individual control measures and integrating them complement each other thereby reducing the impact of their disadvantages. With biological control, the effectiveness of natural enemies is variable since the natural enemies are affected by environmental conditions which greatly varies from one environment to the other. Also, the

impact of natural enemies on the insect pests is low and erratic Cultural control is very tedious and laborious.

Although, the most adopted and effective control is chemical control using synthetic insecticides but their use have been widely argued. This is related to the adverse side effect of exposing human population to health hazards and negatively affecting the environment. Sanon *et al.*, 2018 correlated these health risks with lack of training and information for insecticide, overdose application, inadequate use of protective equipment when handling pesticide and poor selection of chemicals by farmers. It is also argued that the residue in the stored produce can cause cancer and adverse reproductive effect when the levels are high (ketoh *et al.*, 2006; Sanon *et al.*, 2018). Development of insecticide resistance, affecting of non-target species and beneficial organisms and polluting of environment are also included in the adverse effect associated with the use of synthetic insecticide.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The importance of integrating the various control measures to control these major insect pests of cowpea has been established. The infestation of insect pests convolutes the production of cowpea which causes drastic loss in yield and marginal returns at all stages of the production and supply chain. The most used measure of controlling these major insect pests is the combination of chemical control with good cultural practices as well as planting of hybrid or resistant varieties. For the chemical control, organophosphates are mostly used since they are environmentally benign than the others and are readily available. Spraying is normally done three times once during budding, flowering and podding. Also, the most adopted cultural practices are weed control, early planting and harvesting, suitable plant density and good storage facility. Also, farmers prefer better varieties once it's readily available to them. Also, the most used botanicals are various neem extracts at various concentration and are sprayed more than three times during production. In the store, fumigants are the most preferred synthetic insecticide since they bring fast and reliable results.

5.2 Recommendation

Information and benefits of adopting the Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies should be made easily accessible to farmers through organizing of seminars, forming of association and demonstrating the benefits gained using farmers who has adopted these strategies.

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